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Mapping Data Skills Frameworks for Australian Social Science Research

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Project work package lead

Tomasz Zając

The Social Science Research Infrastructure Network acknowledges the Traditional Owners and their custodianship of the lands on which we work. We pay our respects to their Ancestors and their descendants, who continue cultural and spiritual connections to Country

Contents

Abbreviations used in text for framework titles	5
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Methodology.....	10
3 Australian frameworks and guidelines	13
3.1 General data skills.....	17
3.2 Spatial data.....	20
3.3 Data governance	23
3.4 Artificial intelligence.....	25
3.5 What we learnt.....	28
4 Indigenous data governance documents	31
5 International frameworks.....	35
5.1 International data skills framework to inform research.....	37
5.2 International data skills framework to inform policy making and industry	41
5.3 International frameworks for professional development in data science and analytics	45
5.4 What we learnt from the review of international data skills frameworks.....	48
6 Research Software Engineering in Social Science Research	49
7 Summary.....	54
References	57
Appendices.....	59
Appendix A. Tables outlining reviewed frameworks	59
Table 1 Australian frameworks and guidelines	59
Table 2- Global frameworks and guidelines.....	67
Table 3 Research Software Engineering frameworks and guidelines	72
Table 4 Frameworks and guidelines for Indigenous data governance	76

Figures

Figure 1 Overview of the reviewed guidelines and frameworks.....	12
Figure 2 Reviewed Australian digital and data skills frameworks and guides by year of publication	13
Figure 3 Reviewed Australian digital and data skills frameworks by type of publishing institution	14
Figure 4 Intended audience of the reviewed Australian digital research and data skills frameworks and guides	16
Figure 5 The frequency of the main themes in the reviewed Australian digital research and data skills frameworks and guides	17
Figure 6 The frequency of non-Australian reviewed frameworks by country	37

Abbreviations used in text for framework titles

SSR: Social Science Research
 ADSSSF: Australia Data Skills for Social Science Framework
 SSRIN: Social Science Research Infrastructure Network
 RSE: Research Software Engineering
 ACMA DSGF: ACMA Data Strategy and Governance Framework
 ACS DSF: ACS Data Sharing Framework
 ACSQHC DGF: ACSQHC Data Governance Framework
 ACT DGMF: ACT Data Governance and Management Framework
 ADCF: Australian Digital Capability Framework
 ADSSSF: Australian Data Skills for Social Sciences Framework
 AEHF: AI Ethics Framework
 AFGAIS: Australian Framework for Generative Artificial Intelligence in Schools
 AGR-DAUI: Australian Government Response to Data Availability and Use Inquiry
 AHPF: Australian Health Performance Framework
 AI AEF: Artificial Intelligence: Australia's Ethics Framework
 AI RMF 1.0: Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework
 AI-EF UoM: Artificial Intelligence: Australia's Ethics Framework – University of Melbourne Response
 AIHF: Artificial Intelligence Framework
 AIHW DGF: AIHW Data Governance Framework
 ANZ FSDF: Australian and New Zealand Foundation Spatial Data Framework
 APS DCF: APS Data Capability Framework
 ARDC DRCSF: ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework
 ATI CHTF: The Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Cultural and Health Training Framework
 CARE PIDG: The CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance
 CF-AIL: A Competency Framework for AI Literacy: Variations by Different Learner Groups and an Implied Learning Pathway
 DALI DLF: DALI Data Literacy Framework
 DATA: Data Availability and Transparency Act
 DCF: Data capacity framework
 DDGS: Data and Digital Government Strategy
 DDMF: De-Identification Decision-Making Framework
 DEF: Data Exchange Framework
 DE DS: Department of Education Data Strategy
 DEWR DS: Department of Employment and Workplace Relations Data Strategy
 DGF-WGEA: Data Governance Framework – Workplace Gender Equality Agency
 DGFA: The Data Governance Framework Appendix
 DGA: Data Governance in Australia
 Digital, Data and Technology Playbook: DDaT Playbook
 DLSF: Digital Literacy Skills Framework
 DQF-DMI: Data Quality Framework for the Australian Government's Direct Measure of Income
 DS 2021–2024: Data Strategy 2021–2024

DS ANRMI: Digital Skills for All Non-IT Roles Across Multiple Industries
 DS-BoK: The Data Science Body of Knowledge
 DSCF: Data Science Competency Framework
 DSF: Data Skills Framework
 DSFP: Digital Skills Frameworks and Programs
 DTHA-C: Digital Transformation of Healthcare in Australia – Constrained
 EAIA-ASD: Ethical Artificial Intelligence in the Australian Signals Directorate
 ECR ATPC: The Ethical Conduct in Research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait
 Islander Peoples and Communities
 EDS: Enterprise Data Strategy 2024–27
 ESRC- DDS: ESRC Data-Driven Research Skills
 FAIRAF: Foundational Artificial Intelligence Risk Assessment Framework
 FGID: Framework for Governance of Indigenous Data
 FSG-MHR: Framework to Guide the Secondary Use of My Health Record System
 Data
 GF-DE SA: Governance Framework – Department for Education South Australia
 GIDOESS: Governance of Indigenous data in open earth systems science
 HCF: Hosting Certification Framework
 ICT NT: ICT Navigation Tool
 IDS: Indigenous Data Sovereignty Communique
 IES: Indigenous Evaluation Strategy
 IDSP: Indigenous Data Sovereignty Policy Brief
 IoA ACF: Institute of Analytics Analyst Competency Framework
 Jisc BDCF: Jisc Building Digital Capabilities Framework
 JNCC: Joint Nature Conservation Committee
 KRT II: Keeping research on track II
 NAA IMDC: National Archives of Australia – Information Management and Data
 Capabilities
 NCF DPHC: The National Competency Framework for Data Professionals in Health
 and Care
 NDSF: National Digital Skills Framework
 NFA-AIG: National Framework for the Assurance of Artificial Intelligence in
 Government
 NFS-RASDA: National Framework for the Sharing of Restricted Access Species Data
 in Australia
 NHRA DMF: Natural Hazards Research Australia Data Management Framework
 NIST AIRMF: NIST Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework
 NIST RDF: NIST Research Data Framework
 NSW GDS: NSW Government Data Strategy
 NSW IDMF: NSW Infrastructure Data Management Framework
 NWMPHN DGF: NWMPHN Data Governance Framework
 OAIC DS: OAIC Data Strategy
 OECD FDTS: The OECD Framework for digital talent and skills in the public sector
 OECD SS: OECD Skills Strategy Framework
 ODPG: Open Data Process Guide
 PSF: Putting Skills First
 Q2RM: QUADRANT 2 Research Management

QUKDSG: Quantifying the UK Data Skills Gap
RAI-ESG: The Intersection of Responsible AI and ESG: A Framework for Investor
RDMFI: Research Data Management Framework for Institutions
RDMP: Research Data Management Procedure
RDMPF: Research Data Management Policy Framework
RRP SEDC: Researcher Role Profile: Six Elements of Digital Capabilities
RSDF: Research Skill Development Framework
SCF: Skills and Capability Framework
SDTF: Sharing Data in Trusted Frameworks
SF ICT: The Skills Framework for ICT
SSNS-DDR: The Skills Needed in the Social Sciences to Support Data-Driven
Research Across the Lifecourse
TCOD: Taking Control of Our Data
TFF: The Foundational Four
TIMBC: The Indigenous Metadata Bundle Communiqué
UFC AEE: Uplifting FAIR and CARE Across Earth and Environmental Science Data
UK SCF: Skills and Competency Framework
UKDS DSF: UKDS Data Skills Framework
UN GWG: The UN Global Working Group on Big Data for Official Statistics
Competency Framework
VUDF: Victoria Unearthed Data Framework
VPDSF: Victorian Protective Data Security Framework
VPS IMF: Information Management Framework for the Victorian Public Service
WA AI Policy: Artificial Intelligence Policy – Western Australian Government
WA AI-AF: WA Government Artificial Intelligence Assurance Framework
WA IMF: Information Management Framework for Western Australia
WADSIH DSCF: WADSIH Data Science Competency Framework
WB DSP: World Bank’s Digital Skills Frameworks and Programs
WTRRDM: Waipapa Taumata Rau Research Data Management Capability Maturity
Model
YPEAP: Yurirka: Proppa Engagement with Aboriginal Peoples

1 Introduction

Social science research (SSR) is increasingly becoming data-driven. This shift requires the skills to work effectively with data, communicate results, and treat data as a valuable national asset (Cotterell & von Randow, 2010¹). Working effectively in this environment requires social science researchers to be able to choose the most appropriate type of data to inform their research, rather than relying solely on data that are already available to them and with which they are familiar. Doing so, social science researchers should be provided with opportunities to identify the skill sets they need, and second, training opportunities to develop these specific skills.

To address these needs, a comprehensive and coordinated data skills framework for SSR can significantly assist both individuals and training providers in identifying the relevant data-related skills. One of the Activity streams in the Social Science Research Infrastructure Network (SSRIN) project aims to create a data skills framework tailored to the needs of social science researchers and capable of guiding them across different stages of the data lifecycle. This report maps the current landscape of data skills frameworks applicable to the Australian context and reviews Research Software Engineer (RSE) career and skills frameworks. The review aimed to identify key themes and data skills covered by these documents as well as gaps in the existing frameworks. It will contribute to the development of the Australian Data Skills for Social Sciences Framework (ADSSSF) which is another planned output of SSRIN.

We reviewed both Australian and non-Australian data skills frameworks to identify relevant skills and how these skills can be structured, embedded, delivered, and maintained. We identified aspects in the skills frameworks outlining how organisations structure and support data skills, and about data governance, management, and use. Documents were included if they covered these concepts and were clearly relevant to SSR, even if they were not initially designed for it. The frameworks analysed were

¹ Cotterell, G., & von Randow, M. (2010). Addressing the quantitative skill shortage in the social sciences. *New Zealand Science Review*, 67(4), 126-128.

developed by academic, government, non-governmental, and collaborative bodies, as well as specialised agencies and institutions.

As previously stated, another feature of this document is providing a comprehensive overview of the role of RSE skills and career frameworks in supporting skills development for SSR. The review revealed that those frameworks often stress the importance of reproducibility, long-term infrastructural sustainability, and collaborative research environments. The growing complexity of data practices has led to this orientation towards the critical role of RSE in computationally intensive social science practices (Gardiner et al., 2018)².

To be applicable to the Australian context, the current document includes the review of frameworks relevant to the governance, management and use of Indigenous data. Most of these documents are primarily produced by Indigenous-led organisations. This is an essential part of this document because, in the Australian and other postcolonial contexts, it is essential for social science researchers to understand how to collect, manage, and analyse Indigenous data in an ethical and culturally sensitive way. The review revealed that this topic is not covered comprehensively in existing data skills frameworks, and although these skills must be viewed as part of data skills, the relevant documents are often shaped in isolation from the remaining landscape of data skills frameworks.

In this document, we review a range of data skills frameworks that offer valuable insights for developing an Australian data skills framework for social science research. However, the review also identifies several gaps that are relevant to ADSSSF. These include the absence of an Australian framework designed specifically for social science researchers, the limited translation of broad concepts such as data literacy and capability into discipline-specific competencies, uneven attention to qualitative and mixed-methods research, and the separation of data skills frameworks from Indigenous

² Gardiner, A., Aasheim, C., Rutner, P., & Williams, S. (2018). Skill requirements in big data: A content analysis of job advertisements. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 58(4), 374-384.

data governance and Research Software Engineering frameworks. These gaps suggest the need for a framework that is both social science-focused and practically implementable through training pathways, role-based guidance, and sustainable support mechanisms.

The report begins with a methodology section outlining the selection and review process. The next part reviews Australian digital research and data skills frameworks and guidance documents. It identifies the key arguments, approaches and areas for improvement in data skills frameworks for SSR. Section 4 examines how Indigenous data governance is positioned and discussed within national frameworks. The fifth section explores the international digital and data skills landscape to add insight from global practices. Section 6 reviews the role of research software engineers (RSEs) in supporting the technical needs of SSR. The report concludes with a summary of findings and how they can inform ADSSSF. Abbreviations are used for each document after the first mention in this report, with a guide to each abbreviation in Appendix A.

2 Methodology

The first step for this review is to clarify the definition and borders of SSR. SSR often refers to studying society, institutions and human behaviour. The precision and value of SSR largely depend on the accessibility and availability of appropriate data, as well as the researcher's skills to apply the data in an effective way to address the research questions.

Addressing complex research questions in SSR requires the ability to access and work with different types of data, including qualitative, quantitative and spatial data, to explore complex social patterns and inform policy, practice, and theory. This requires skills such as data management, statistical analysis, coding, metadata creation, data visualisation, AI literacy, and research software tools. However, it also includes an understanding of ethics, data governance and cultural value and sensitivity of data.

This review draws on a broad range of publicly available sources, including national and international frameworks, government and institutional websites, databases, and grey

literature such as internal reports, policy briefs, and strategic documents. The review spans the period from 2014 to 2024. Frameworks and guidelines were selected purposively, based on their relevance to digital research and data skills, with particular attention to the needs of SSR.

Initially, we identified three highly relevant data and digital research skills frameworks: the ARDC Digital Research Skills framework (Unsworth, 2024); the UK Data Service Data Skills Framework for Working with Large-Scale Survey Data, Census, and Macro-level Aggregate Data (Higgins et al., 2024)³ and SFIA: The global skills and competency framework for the digital world (2024). Using these texts as starting points for key concepts and vocabulary, we used backward citation and web search to identify further works for consideration.

Additionally, general data skills and digital research frameworks covered some key aspects relevant to SSR in less depth than would be required by many researchers. To consider a more detailed treatment for some topics, documents focusing on a single aspect, rather than all data skills, were reviewed. These included works focusing solely on Indigenous data governance, Artificial Intelligence, geospatial data and Research Software Engineering. Some frameworks and guides with far wider coverage than data skills included smaller, relevant sections. Topical parts of these documents were considered, for example, health sector guides outlining the use and structure of sensitive data or government policy documents discussing data security and privacy.

While “framework” generally refers to highly structured taxonomic documents that systemically describe a domain, several documents we have reviewed had “framework” in the title with a much more narrative structure. Some other documents were very framework-like, but without “framework” in the title. We included a document if useful insight could be gained about domain elements (e.g. data skills or Indigenous data), regardless of title or whether it included wider topical coverage.

³ Higgins, V., Price, D., & King-Hele, S. (2024). The UK Data Service Data Skills Framework for working with large-scale survey data, census, and macro-level aggregate data.

We began by identifying frameworks and documents that address digital research or data skills across various sectors in Australia, including industry, government, education, and research, identifying 59 documents. These documents were examined to understand the overarching landscape of data skills and to identify existing gaps in supporting social science researchers. In parallel, we reviewed 36 international frameworks published in English to draw lessons from global experiences and assess their potential relevance to building capacity in the Australian context.

A key area of focus in the Australian data landscape is Indigenous data. We examined how national data and data skills frameworks address Indigenous perspectives and inclusivity. To enrich this analysis, we also reviewed 31 Indigenous data frameworks, documents, and papers, aiming to extract insights that could inform elements of a data skills framework for social sciences.

Another important priority area is ensuring the sustainability of the systems that generate, analyse and store research data throughout its lifecycle, both in Australia and globally. This requires close collaboration between social science researchers and RSEs. We reviewed frameworks, documents, and job descriptions that discussed the role of RSEs to examine how their roles are defined and how effectively they are positioned to support SSR. We included 32 documents in this section, bringing the total number of reviewed documents in the four sections to 159 (Figure 1). Tables 1 to 4 in the Appendix list all the reviewed documents.

Figure 1 Overview of the reviewed guidelines and frameworks

Each document was assessed using a structured analysis table (see Tables 1 to 4 in Appendix A), recording its potential contribution to capability development. While reviewing the frameworks, we were primarily interested in the types of skills they cover,

how they are organised, and how detailed they are. We also collected contextual information such as who created the framework, the intended audience, the type of data covered, and the skills and capabilities included.

While this document maps the existing frameworks, the review also aims to identify relevant skills. We list them in a separate document–Skill catalogue. The catalogue will provide a comprehensive list of skills that the reviewed documents mention. While not all of them are mentioned in relation to research or even more specifically SSR, it provides a valuable foundation for developing a data skills framework for SSR.

3 Australian frameworks and guidelines

In total, we reviewed 59 Australian digital and data skills frameworks. Most of the reviewed documents were published recently, in the last five years. As Figure 2 shows, 83% were published in 2020 or later, with the highest number published in 2023 (14 documents). This increase in more recent years demonstrates a growing awareness of the importance of data skills.

Figure 2 Reviewed Australian digital and data skills frameworks and guides by year of publication

The documents were developed by a wide range of institutions. The largest number of frameworks have been developed by Commonwealth and State government departments, including agencies such as the federal Department of Health, the federal

Department of Education, the Office of the Australian Information Commissioner, the Department of Employment and Workplace Relations, and the Australian Public Service Commission. See Figure 3 for a breakdown of authorship affiliation. The collection also includes contributions from research data infrastructure facilities such as the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), research organisations such as the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), universities including the University of Canberra, La Trobe University, and the University of Sydney, as well as professional and cross-sectoral bodies such as the Australian Computer Society, the Western Australia Data Science Innovation Hub, and Natural Hazards Research Australia.

Figure 3 Reviewed Australian digital and data skills frameworks by type of publishing institution

The frameworks are also diverse in their intended audiences, as outlined in Figure 4. Audiences include public, research, and technical domains, and many documents have been created with multiple audiences in mind. Several frameworks, such as the ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework (DRCSF), Research Data Management Framework for Institutions (RDMFI), and Research Data Management Policy Framework (RDMPF), are aimed at researchers, academic institutions, and research infrastructure providers, offering structured guidance for data stewardship, data lifecycle planning, and skills development. Others, including the APS Data Capability Framework (APS DCF) and the Australian Data Strategy (ADS), are focused on public sector agencies and government staff, focusing on improving data use,

governance, and capability across the Australian public service. A subset of frameworks, such as the Framework to Guide the Secondary Use of My Health Record System Data (FSG-MHR) and AIHW Data Governance Framework (AIHW DGF), is intended for health departments, clinicians, data custodians, and ethics committees involved in managing and reusing health data under regulated conditions. Technical capability frameworks like the WADSIH Western Australian Data Science Innovation Hub Data Science Competency Framework (WADSIH DSCF) are designed for data science professionals, hiring managers, and training providers to support workforce development in analytics and AI-related roles. Finally, examples such as the Data and Digital Government Strategy (DDGS) and the Data Availability and Transparency Act (DATA) extend their focus to cross-sector stakeholders, including public agencies, private sector actors, academic institutions, and civil society, with a focus on safe data sharing, digital maturity, and system-wide interoperability. Government and policymakers are among the key audiences of the reviewed documents, with 21 and 16 documents, respectively. Researchers are another important audience, with 17 frameworks designed with them in mind. However, we have not identified any Australian data skills framework that is specifically designed for social science researchers and their specific needs to work with data.

Figure 4: Audience of the reviewed Australian digital research and data skills frameworks and guides

These documents each address different themes, with some covering more than one. Figure 5 illustrates the frequency of the main themes covered by the reviewed frameworks. We used these themes to create a typology of frameworks. We have grouped these frameworks based on their similarities, including: 1) those discussing general data skills (including some that are not labelled data skills frameworks), 2) those discussing data governance, privacy and security, 3) frameworks emphasising spatial data, and 4) those with a particular focus on Artificial Intelligence. In the following subsections, we present a summary of our review of the content of the frameworks in each group, with selected documents described in more detail. These examples were selected because they provided the most comprehensive and relevant insights for our review objectives. The frameworks can inform developing the Australian data skills SSR.

Figure 5 The frequency of the main themes in the reviewed Australian data skills frameworks

3.1 General data skills

This section reviews a range of existing frameworks that support the development of general data-related skills and capabilities. We have reviewed them with particular attention to the themes relevant to social science research. Not all these frameworks are explicitly labelled as data skills frameworks. Some are more general data frameworks. Nevertheless, they contribute substantially to the discourse on data literacy, competency development, and institutional preparedness for data-driven practice.

The ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework (ARDC DRCSF) is a comprehensive contribution to the data skills landscape, and for this reason, was used as one of the three key documents to identify initial terms and concepts for further search. Although its focus is not specifically on SSR, it provides a structured understanding of digital research capabilities across different roles such as researchers, data stewards, software engineers, and infrastructure professionals. Importantly, this framework offers a comprehensive list of skills that each role (defined in the document) requires from foundational to advanced levels and links these skills to concrete tasks

and institutional planning. It spans technical (e.g. programming, metadata, data licensing), methodological (e.g. open science, reproducibility), collaborative, and ethical considerations. It is designed to inform national infrastructure, training programs, and research workflows, and serves as a very clear model for aligning skills with the research lifecycle.

Another important national data skills framework is the Australian Digital Capability Framework (ADCF). This is a very structured and detailed competency model, but unlike ARDC DRCSF, it does not link the skills to job roles. It remains a highlighted framework to inform this review, nevertheless, because it groups 21 capabilities into five focus areas, including: data and information literacy, digital communication and collaboration, content creation, protection and safety, and technical problem-solving. Similar to ARDC DRCSF, this framework also organises capabilities across proficiency levels, from foundation to specialised. For each capability at each proficiency level, it includes explicit skills such as metadata analysis, content licensing, scripting, troubleshooting, and digital innovation. Addressing the training needs of social science researchers, considering their different levels of proficiency, will enhance the effectiveness of training delivery.

The WADSIH Data Science Competency Framework (WADSIH DSCF) is another noteworthy Australian document to inform SSR. Although intended for Western Australian industries, it has a multidisciplinary approach that makes it applicable nationally and adaptable to ADSSSF. Similar to the two frameworks above, this also structures the capabilities across three major domains, this time dividing them between data engineering, data analytics, and machine learning/artificial intelligence sciences. The competency framework includes concrete analytical skills such as machine learning, coding, visualisation, and statistical modelling. It maps these against domain knowledge and communication capabilities. The comprehensive approach of this framework to data science roles and skill progression offers a useful model for structuring technical competencies in ADSSSF.

“Data science is not a single discipline, but rather a diverse ecosystem of roles, methodologies and tools sitting across many fields of study”

WADSIH DSCF, P.4

Unlike the detailed approach of the three frameworks above, which were designed to provide highly technical or domain-specific guidance, some documents considered were still useful, some adopt a broader strategic or policy-oriented perspective. The APS DCF provides an example of this. Its key difference from frameworks like WADSIH DCSF and ARDC DRCSF is that this framework specifically discusses administrative data for the public sector. It emphasises general data literacy across government roles and defines 26 distinct capability areas, such as statistical data analysis, metadata, and data visualisation, each with skill indicators at foundational, intermediate, and advanced levels. The framework defines an advanced level as the ability to develop novel models and custom scripting in statistical computing languages. Its broader approach integrates subject matter expertise for policy, regulatory, and service delivery contexts, offering a clear link between data governance and workforce capability development across the Australian Public Service. This is particularly important for those social science researchers who aim to work with administrative data, specifically data from the public sector.

The Foundational Four Framework (FFF) provides another example of a policy-driven document, which is still informative for SSR. Although it does not offer a competency or skills-based structure, it provides a high-level organisational approach focused on initiating cultural and operational change in public sector agencies. Centred on four pillars of leadership, strategy, governance, and asset discovery. This framework can inform the structural foundations needed to enhance data maturity and accountability, which is a significant consideration when working with data, and SSR is no exception. This ensures that data is managed systematically, ethically, and transparently throughout its lifecycle, allowing reliable, reproducible findings.

Another policy-focused document is the Australian Health Performance Framework (AHPF), which informs and guides institutional performance. Although it does not focus on technical or analytical skills, its emphasis on indicator development, disaggregated reporting, and outcome-based evaluation makes it a relevant model for understanding how data skills contribute to strategic public value in health research and evaluation. This is similarly required for SSR to evaluate the research outcome and ensure its effectiveness, equity, and impact, particularly in informing policy and addressing social issues.

The reviewed frameworks in this section demonstrate a growing emphasis across sectors on building structured and strategic approaches to data capability, performance evaluation, and digital transformation. Whether focused on workforce skills or system-level performance, each framework reinforces the critical role of data in driving informed decision-making, accountability, and public value. Notably, the ARDC DRCSF specifically targets research roles, offering structured guidance for researchers, data scientists, and digital research infrastructure professionals. Across all frameworks, the importance of leadership, governance, strategic direction, and measurable outcomes is consistently emphasised, reflecting a national agenda to strengthen data maturity and ensure researchers are equipped to meet the demands of a data-driven future.

3.2 Spatial data

Location-based and spatial data are particularly important for the social sciences, where the focus has traditionally been on quantitative and qualitative data. Terms such as spatial sociology⁴, spatial anthropology⁵, spatial humanities⁶ or environmental

Such as:

⁴ Fuller, M. G., & Löw, M. (2017). Introduction: An invitation to spatial sociology. *Current sociology*, 65(4), 469-491.

⁵ Roberts, L. (2012). Mapping cultures: A spatial anthropology. In *Mapping cultures: Place, practice, performance* (pp. 1-25). London: Palgrave Macmillan UK.

⁶ Bodenhamer, D. J., Corrigan, J., & Harris, T. M. (Eds.). (2010). *The spatial humanities: GIS and the future of humanities scholarship*. Indiana University Press.

psychology⁷ and many other terms across social science studies, such as political science⁸, all indicate that the significance of understanding place (or/and space) goes beyond geography and urban studies. Place/space plays a central role in social science studies, as they influence and is influenced by human interactions. In this regard, if we define social science research as studying society, institutions and human behaviour, then place/space becomes an inseparable part of social science studies, such as sociology, criminology, psychology, anthropology and political science⁹. It requires integrating spatial methods into mixed-methods research to address more complex questions. Reviewing frameworks that incorporate spatial data is a valuable way to identify the potential of spatial analysis, and ADSSSF can adapt these insights to support SSR.

The reviewed frameworks demonstrate growing recognition of spatial data's value and offer promising components for future integration. To be more useful for SSR, spatial

⁷ Ayaghihchi, H. (2007). The contribution of space syntax to a comprehensive theory of environmental psychology. ..., *6th International Space Syntax*....

⁸ Reynolds, D. R. (1994). Political geography: the power of place and the spatiality of politics. *Progress in Human Geography*, 18(2), 234-247.

⁹ Such as:

Low, S. M. (2011). Claiming space for an engaged anthropology: Spatial inequality and social exclusion. *American anthropologist*, 113(3), 389-407.

Brown, G., Raymond, C. M., & Corcoran, J. (2015). Mapping and measuring place attachment. *Applied Geography*, 57, 42-53.

Corcoran, J., Li, T., Rohde, D., Charles-Edwards, E., & Mateo-Babiano, D. (2014). Spatio-temporal patterns of a Public Bicycle Sharing Program: the effect of weather and calendar events. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 41, 292-305.

Brunsdon, C., Corcoran, J., & Higgs, G. (2007). Visualising space and time in crime patterns: A comparison of methods. *Computers, environment and urban systems*, 31(1), 52-75.

Kimpton, A. (2018). The sociability of urban greenspace: an exploration of how public parks and private backyards influence the social sustainability of urban communities.

Sigler, T., Mahmuda, S., Kimpton, A., Loginova, J., Wohland, P., Charles-Edwards, E., & Corcoran, J. (2021). The socio-spatial determinants of COVID-19 diffusion: the impact of globalisation, settlement characteristics and population. *Globalization and health*, 17(1), 56.

Sigler, T., & Wachsmuth, D. (2016). Transnational gentrification: Globalisation and neighbourhood change in Panama's Casco Antiguo. *Urban Studies*, 53(4), 705-722.

Roberts, L. (2012). Mapping cultures: A spatial anthropology. In *Mapping cultures: Place, practice, performance* (pp. 1-25). London: Palgrave Macmillan UK.

Aase, T. H. (1994). Symbolic space: Representations of space in geography and anthropology. *Geografiska Annaler: Series B, Human Geography*, 76(1), 51-58.

data components of frameworks need to put a more deliberate focus on skills that social science researchers need for location-based research. This is particularly because spatial practices support mixed-methods research and reveal social patterns that might be obvious by relying only on traditional quantitative and qualitative methods. Additionally, spatial analysis is an effective tool for communicating findings through visualisation, making research outputs more accessible and understandable to audiences outside the research field.

The Australian and New Zealand Foundation Spatial Data Framework (ANZ FSDF), ADS, VUDF, and DS 2021–2024 all position geospatial data as a critical infrastructure layer across government and public services. Each document acknowledges the importance of spatial data in policy, planning, and public transparency, promoting its integration into decision-making processes and advocating for improved data capability. However, none of them provides structured frameworks for building geospatial skills and integrating them into decision-making and research.

VUDF, as another example, presents a structured model for managing and delivering environmental and spatial data for land use planning. Land use is only a matter of urban studies and geography, but it is widely used in social science studies to explore the socio-spatial phenomena¹⁰. VUDF, therefore, can guide these studies by providing a model for operationalising data governance and spatial data standards, highlighting the value of structured custodianship and interoperability.

These frameworks treat spatial data as essential, but spatial literacy and capability are often assumed rather than explicitly planned for. While they promote spatial integration, they generally lack role-based skill definitions, structured methods, or clear

¹⁰ Such as:

Perin, C. (2014). *Everything in its place: Social order and land use in America*. Princeton University Press.

Platt, R. H. (2014). *Land use and society: Geography, law, and public policy* (pp. 13-19). Washington, DC: Island Press.

Nabil, N. A., & Abd Eldayem, G. E. (2015). Influence of mixed land-use on realizing the social capital. *HBRC journal*, 11(2), 285-298.

development pathways, highlighting a gap between strategic intent and operational capability building.

3.3 Data governance

One of the most prevalent themes across all the documents is data governance, privacy, and security. While the frameworks reviewed in this section were developed for different purposes other than SSR, their approaches to data governance extend beyond their immediate fields and offer valuable insights for ADSSSF to consider data governance as a core principle in building capacity for data use in SSR. These frameworks outline the rules and structures to ensure privacy and security are maintained when data is managed and shared across sectors. While most documents are concerned with data governance, they vary widely in purpose; some focus on protecting sensitive information, others on enabling open data access, and a few on building the workforce capabilities needed to support responsible data practices. These documents help to identify competencies necessary for responsible social sciences research, although they are rarely identified as ‘skills frameworks’.

Several documents address data governance in health and human services. For instance, FSG-MHR, AIHW DGF, and ACSQHC Data Governance Framework (ACSQHC DGF) provide detailed procedures for the ethical use of personal and health data. These documents include strict criteria for consent, authorisation, risk assessment, and de-identification standards. The De-Identification Decision-Making Framework (DDMF) specifically adds further precision by outlining formal techniques, such as suppression, pseudonymisation, and contextual risk analysis, to assess re-identification risks. These frameworks provide valuable technical considerations and privacy-preserving methods (e.g., k-anonymity). These methods are also necessary for social science researchers who may engage with sensitive data and health data for their research purposes.

Other documents, such as the Information Management Framework for Western Australia (WA IMF), Victorian Protective Data Security Framework (VPDSF), NSW Infrastructure Data Management Framework (NSW IDMF), ACS Data Sharing Framework (ACS DSF), Sharing Data in Trusted Frameworks (SDTF), Data Availability

and Transparency Act (DATA), and Australian Government Response to Data Availability and Use Inquiry (AGR-DAUI), are not skills frameworks in a narrow sense. They are included here because they define governance conditions that shape how social science researchers may access, manage, share, protect, and reuse data, particularly when working with administrative, linked, sensitive, or cross-sector datasets. These documents highlight principles such as data custodianship, clear role definition, stewardship hierarchies, asset registers, secure classification, and trusted access models. For ADSSSF, their value lies not in providing direct competency lists, but in identifying the governance knowledge that researchers may need to navigate responsible data use in practice. This includes understanding data access conditions, privacy obligations, custodianship arrangements, risk classification, legal responsibilities, and secure data-sharing environments.

In the research domain, documents like the Research Data Management Policy Framework (RDMPF), Research Data Management Framework for Institutions (RDMFI), and Natural Hazards Research Australia Data Management Framework (NHRA DMF) attend to the data lifecycle component of data governance. They provide detailed guidance across stages, including planning, metadata documentation, repository deposit, long-term archiving, and licensing for reuse. They reference standards such as DataCite¹¹ DOIs and recommend the use of platforms like RDMP¹², ReDBox¹³, and RDM¹⁴. This method-based approach offers significant insight to ensure social science researchers effectively manage the data lifecycle using the tailored methods and standards. Similarly, other frameworks, such as the National Archives of Australia, Information Management and Data Capabilities (NAA IMDC), and the Digital

11 Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) issued by DataCite, an international organisation that registers and manages persistent identifiers specifically for research data and other scholarly outputs.

12 Research Data Management Plans

13 Australian-made research data management platform developed by QCIF (Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation).

14 Institutional Research Data Management

Literacy Skills Framework (DLSF) provide additional useful guidance for metadata management throughout the data lifecycle.

Meanwhile, some frameworks focus on open data governance, such as the Open Data Process Guide (ODPG) and the Data Exchange Framework (DEF). They promote interoperability, discoverability, and public reusability of data. They outline foundational principles for data privacy and management, such as API-based access, standardised metadata, and the proactive release of non-sensitive datasets. While both frameworks support the incorporation of open data, each brings a specific focus. The ODPG focuses on data management, privacy governance, and metadata creation. It also addresses data classification with respect to security, availability, and integrity, along with quality assessment, de-identification techniques, and legal reviews related to copyright and third-party rights. The DEF serves as a data-sharing protocol between service providers and the government, supporting a privacy-aware and outcome-focused model. Nevertheless, privacy is a significant theme that researchers, particularly those working with sensitive data, need to consider¹⁵. Therefore, reviewing this group of frameworks seem necessary for developing ADSSSF to explore how other frameworks address data privacy.

3.4 Artificial intelligence

Another emerging theme across the reviewed documents is the growing significance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in data skills. AI increasingly shapes the landscape of data and data skills across different fields, and social science is no exception. Including AI in data skills frameworks for SSR is significantly important not only because of its growing influence on how data is generated, analysed, and interpreted, but also due to the social and ethical implications that arise from its application. As AI-driven tools such as

¹⁵ Such as:

Heffetz, O., & Ligett, K. (2014). Privacy and data-based research. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 28(2), 75-98.

Chen, B. C., Kifer, D., LeFevre, K., & Machanavajjhala, A. (2009). Privacy-preserving data publishing. *Foundations and trends in databases*, 2(1-2), 1-167.

Lowrance, W. (2003). Learning from experience: privacy and the secondary use of data in health research. *Journal of health services research & policy*, 8(1_suppl), 2-7.

machine learning, natural language processing, and predictive analytics are adopted in social research, researchers must be equipped to critically engage with these technologies. AI literacy is not just about technical knowledge but also about developing critical thinking, ethical awareness, and the ability to navigate AI systems in informed and responsible ways (Chee et al., 2024¹⁶). In alignment with this perspective, we have reviewed 15 frameworks to understand the opportunities and the challenges that are associated with AI for SSR data skills.

Several Australian frameworks offer guidance on the ethical and responsible use of AI, each with different levels of emphasis on governance and operational implementation. They reinforce the existing data skills with attention to AI-related risks, values, and regulatory concerns. This reinforces a key pattern across the AI-focused frameworks reviewed: while they highlight the importance of ethical and responsible AI, they offer little in terms of structured, role-based skills development or actionable training pathways.

As an example, the National Library of Australia's Artificial Intelligence Framework (AIF) demonstrates a commitment to ethical use of AI, focusing on key concerns such as privacy, copyright, intellectual property, and cybersecurity. It also addresses organisational change and proposes a unified approach to AI training and capability development in response to its workflows and staff competencies. With the same concern, the AI Ethics Framework (AI-EF) highlights ethical principles, including human oversight, explainability, and institutional responsibility. These concerns should also be reflected in the application of AI for SSR to inform ADSSSF. The different requirements of AI-enabled research, including the associated opportunities and risks, highlighted a need for reviewing data governance in AI frameworks separately.

¹⁶ Chee, H., Ahn, S., & Lee, J. (2025). A competency framework for AI literacy: Variations by different learner groups and an implied learning pathway. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 56(5), 2146-2182.

To ensure accountability of research with the application of AI, one crucial factor is human supervision. There are many studies and frameworks that emphasise on the role of human supervision that offer insight into SSR. For example, the Artificial Intelligence Policy, Western Australian Government (WA AI Policy) outlines six principles: human-centred values, fairness, transparency, privacy, accountability, and reliability, intended to apply throughout the AI system lifecycle. A similar approach is Ethical Artificial Intelligence in the Australian Signals Directorate (EAIA-ASD), which puts more emphasis on the human role, particularly in cybersecurity and intelligence analysis. It defines five core principles, including lawfulness, human oversight, reliability, fairness, and accountability. These principles are supported by internal and external mechanisms, such as the data, technology and infrastructure committee and operational compliance committee, as well as external mechanisms including the Inspector-General of Intelligence and Security and the Parliamentary Joint Committee on Intelligence and Security. More importantly, it discusses challenges such as bias, model drift, and securing AI systems and aims to guide ethical deployment in intelligence and cyber contexts. It is also a risk assurance and governance tool rather than a capacity-building framework.

Another topic that needs to be taken into account in AI-focused frameworks to inform SSR is risk management and transparency. Frameworks such as, The National Framework for the Assurance of AI in Government (NFA-AIG) and Queensland's Foundational AI Risk Assessment Framework (FAIRAF) offer structured approaches to risk management, transparency, and accountability in using AI. These frameworks foreground governance mechanisms such as risk classification, auditability, and compliance. The FAIRAF in particular, adds more detail by including a component-based and values-driven assessment model, which guides users through evaluating AI solutions in relation to technical architecture, human-machine interaction, sector-specific obligations, and legislative context. It helps to map risks and mitigate them across the AI lifecycle and embeds this analysis within SSR. Another AI governance-oriented framework with a focus on risk assessment is the NIST Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework (NIST AIRMF), which aims to address risks such as bias, lack of transparency, privacy violations, and system failures.

The reviewed AI-focused frameworks underscore the growing importance of AI in shaping data skills for research. While there is an agreement on the need for ethical and responsible AI use, their approaches vary; some focus on high-level principles and organisational governance, while others focus on risk management and cultural considerations. Although the application of AI has been discussed thoroughly in the literature (e.g., Grassmann et al., 2023¹⁷ and Xu et al., 2024¹⁸), ADSSSF has an opportunity to offer actionable, skill-based strategies for the application of AI tailored to the needs of SSR. Additionally, ADSSSF needs to discuss the limitations of AI compared to human cognitive ability.

3.5 What we learnt

Despite the fact that there are valuable works to promote digital data skills in the Australian landscape, there is a substantial gap for SSR. None of the reviewed frameworks in Australia has been specifically designed for use by social science researchers. Nevertheless, their emphasis on data linkage, research roles and software development provides valuable insight for ADSSSF to tailor data skills to researchers at different levels of data literacy. Although findings by Vodă et al. (2022)¹⁹ reveal that social science students often possess stronger technical digital, communication, and problem-solving skills than their humanities peers, their distinctive needs remain poorly supported in Australian data skills frameworks. This reflects a broader trend in SSR, where mixed methods are essential to address the complexity of social phenomena. As such, there is a pressing need for a dedicated framework that acknowledges the

¹⁷ Grossmann, I., Feinberg, M., Parker, D. C., Christakis, N. A., Tetlock, P. E., & Cunningham, W. A. (2023). AI and the transformation of social science research. *Science*, 380(6650), 1108-1109.

¹⁸ Xu, R., Sun, Y., Ren, M., Guo, S., Pan, R., Lin, H., ... & Han, X. (2024). AI for social science and social science of AI: A survey. *Information Processing & Management*, 61(3), 103665.

¹⁹ Vodă, A. I., Cautisanu, C., Grădinaru, C., Tănăsescu, C., & de Moraes, G. H. S. M. (2022). Exploring digital literacy skills in social sciences and humanities students. *Sustainability*, 14(5), 2483.

diverse, interpretive, and ethically embedded data practices of social science researchers (Barker et al., 2019²⁰; Bowling & Ebrahim, 2005²¹).

While the more recent frameworks acknowledge the use of AI in research, their approach remains focused on its ethical use, rather than how it can inform research, specifically SSR. Although the use of AI in SSR has been thoroughly discussed in the reviewed documents, they are dispersed and not discussed in a comprehensive and structured way to include different types of data and research requirements. These competencies help social scientists ensure that AI systems are developed and deployed in ways that are equitable, transparent, and socially accountable. ADSSSF can fill the existing gaps to build capacity for effective, transparent and meaningful use of data in the Australian SSR landscape.

The ADSSSF can draw several other lessons from this review. While many frameworks recognise the importance of data capability, they often focus on public sector governance, technical roles, or health and infrastructure systems, highlighting the need for a framework that integrates both technical and non-technical skills, including data governance, mixed-method research and the ability to work with RSEs.

The problem is compounded by the use of broad, undefined terms such as “literacy” and “capability,” which are rarely translated into discipline-specific competencies. There are some exceptions, such as the Digital Research Capabilities & Skills Framework, which defines capability as:

²⁰ Barker, M., Wilkinson, R., & Treloar, A. (2019). The Australian research data commons.

²¹ Bowling, A., & Ebrahim, S. (2005). *Handbook of health research methods: investigation, measurement and analysis*. McGraw-Hill Education (UK).

“The ability or capacity of an individual to perform a specific task or function effectively. A capability encompasses a combination of skills, knowledge, experience, and behaviours that enable a person to achieve desired outcomes in their role.”

ARDC DRCSF, 2021. P.7

Limited attention to skill progression is another problem. Competencies are often presented with limited pathways to development, reducing their impact and usability for institutions. The exceptions are APS, ARDC DRCSF, and WADSIH DCFS, which introduced role-based or tiered structures, although even these frameworks could benefit from a more coordinated strategy. Currently, frameworks such as ARDC DRCSF and WADSIH DCFS offer structured, tiered skill development aligned with specific research and roles, while other frameworks, like APS DCF and FAIRAF, focus on governance and risk management without role-specific competency pathways. In this context, a coordinated strategy would ensure these frameworks are not developed in isolation and instead form an integrated data skills landscape.

The complexity of the data landscape today increases the demand for analytical and data skills for SSR. To build a more coherent and comprehensive data skills framework for SSR, Australia would benefit from a national reference model that links sector-specific efforts through shared standards, competency tiers, and flexible learning pathways towards existing and future skills development resources. This would address current needs while enhancing interoperability across research, government, and education. It will also be important to adapt RSE skills and career frameworks to SSR, to support increasingly complex methods and infrastructure. There is an opportunity for ADSSSF to bridge this gap by supporting social science researchers at various levels of data literacy with role-specific guidance, training pathways, and practical tools.

The frameworks reviewed so far in this section do not reflect the critical need for an Australian skills framework to incorporate skills to work with Indigenous data. The documents covered do not include data skills and methods to effect Indigenous data

sovereignty to shape ethical, inclusive, and culturally responsive data practices. This gap suggests an opportunity for a distinctive approach to skills development for digital SSR. The next section examines the potential for the new ADSSSF to include capabilities for working with Indigenous data such as participatory research, appropriate metadata creation, and ethical governance, supporting self-determination and culturally grounded Indigenous data use. Incorporating these principles ensures the framework is not only technically robust but also socially and culturally accountable.

4 Indigenous data governance documents

Australia's colonial history has made Indigenous data a necessary topic of discussion in different fields. It has shaped the ways in which data about Indigenous peoples in Australia is collected, accessed, used and communicated for different purposes (such as research and policy), positioning Australia as a centre of expertise in Indigenous data sovereignty and supporting methods. Any discussion of data and data skills in the Australian context cannot happen without acknowledging Indigenous perspectives.

Indigenous data refers to *“information or knowledge in any format, inclusive of statistics, that is about Indigenous people and that impacts Indigenous lives at the collective and/or individual level”* (Maiam Nayri Wingara Indigenous Data Sovereignty Collective, 2024, p.1). This includes not only data created by or about Indigenous peoples, but also data used to make decisions impacting their lives, and data about the resources and environments of Indigenous peoples.

Walter (2016)²² argues that there is an epistemic problem in how Indigenous peoples in Australia are represented in data, and recommends a fundamental shift in how Indigenous data is governed. This would enhance epistemic sovereignty because sovereignty over data is essential for undoing structural erasure and restoring control over Indigenous narratives. A growing body of frameworks addresses these concerns, with many emphasising data sovereignty, custodianship, stewardship, ownership and

²² Walter, M. (2016). Data politics and Indigenous representation in Australian statistics. In 'Indigenous data sovereignty: toward an agenda'. (Eds T Kukutai, J Taylor) pp. 79–97.

the rights of Indigenous people to govern their own data and determine its ethical use. Others provide more detailed guidance and outlines of specific capabilities and skills needed to manage Indigenous data in ways that support self-determination, cultural values, and community benefit. In this section, we have reviewed 32 (Table 4 in the appendix) frameworks, documents and journal articles concerned with Indigenous data.

Indigenous data sovereignty is among the most discussed themes in frameworks and other documents relevant to Indigenous data. This refers to the right of Indigenous people to control different stages of the data lifecycle, including collection, access, ownership and use. The concept asserts authority and ensures that data reflects the interests and cultural values of Indigenous communities. Among these documents, the Australian Public Service's Framework for Governance of Indigenous Data (FGID) provides a practical guideline for respecting and effecting Indigenous data sovereignty in the Australian public sector. It emphasises the importance of leadership by Indigenous communities, recognising their right to control data across the data lifecycle. It not only relies on consultation with Indigenous communities, but it also recognises shared decision-making about data in partnership with Indigenous people. FGID emphasises data sharing principles of FAIR (Wilkinson et al., 2016²³) and the additional person and purpose-based perspectives of CARE (Carroll et al, 2020²⁴) to ensure data quality and ethical use. It also reiterates Walter's 2018²⁵ framing of deficit-based use of data to impact Indigenous peoples (BADDR; blaming, aggregate, decontextualised, deficit, restricted access). Anderson et al. (2022)²⁶ argue that co-design must reflect Indigenous values and leadership and assert that authentic co-design is only possible when guided by Indigenous cultural authority and practices. The discussion paper on

²³ Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., ... & Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), 1-9.

²⁴ Carroll, S. R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O. L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., ... & Hudson, M. (2020). The CARE principles for indigenous data governance.

²⁵ Walter, M. (2018). The voice of Indigenous data: Beyond the markers of disadvantage. *Griffith Review*, (60), 256-263.

²⁶ Jennings, L., Anderson, T., Martinez, A., Sterling, R., Chavez, D. D., Garba, I., ... & Carroll, S. R. (2023). Applying the 'CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance to ecology and biodiversity research. *Nature ecology & evolution*, 7(10), 1547-1551.

Indigenous data governance produced by the Lowitja Institute, Taking Control of Our Data (TCOD), summarises and outlines key definitions and discussions of Indigenous data sovereignty and governance in Australia, including the need for data literacy, community engagement, and governance planning. Other frameworks that emphasise indigenous data sovereignty are the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Cultural and Health Training Framework (ATI CHTF), the Indigenous Data Sovereignty Communique (IDS), the Indigenous Data Sovereignty Policy Brief (IDSP), the Indigenous Evaluation Strategy (IES), the Data Governance Framework Appendix (DGFA), and Governance of Indigenous Data in Open Earth Systems Science (GIDOESS).

The CARE principles were first articulated by Carroll et al. (2023)²⁷, stating that the FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016²⁸) need to be augmented by considering people and the purpose of data in order to effect Indigenous data sovereignty. The article offers mechanisms for applying CARE principles to data for governance and for the governance of data. It describes 12 principles to promote Indigenous collective benefit, give control, and ensure responsible and ethical data use. These principles can be applied by researchers and institutions responsible for collecting, managing, or sharing Indigenous data. Jennings et al. (2023)²⁹ apply the CARE principles to specific fields of research, such as ecology and biodiversity. Their research recommends developing data management plans that reflect Indigenous protocols and local context. They explored specific skills, including metadata creation and participatory research aligned with CARE principles.

Most of the reviewed frameworks and documents concur that community engagement is essential for Indigenous data sovereignty. Respecting and incorporating Indigenous

²⁷ Carroll, S. R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O. L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., Parsons, M., Raseroka, K., Rodriguez-Lonebear, D., & Rowe, R. (2023). The CARE principles for indigenous data governance. *Open Scholarship Press Curated Volumes: Policy*.

²⁸ Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., & Bourne, P. E. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 1-9.

²⁹ Jennings, L., Anderson, T., Martinez, A., Sterling, R., Chavez, D. D., Garba, I., ... & Carroll, S. R. (2023). Applying the 'CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance' to ecology and biodiversity research. *Nature ecology & evolution*, 7(10), 1547-1551.

worldviews in all aspects of the data lifecycle recognises and reflects the values and priorities of Indigenous communities. An example of this approach is outlined in Uplifting FAIR and CARE Across Earth and Environmental Science Data (UFC AEE) produced by the ARDC. It reiterates the CARE principles that Indigenous data governance must incorporate values such as collective benefit, cultural authority, and ethical responsibility. It highlights that metadata should be capable of reflecting community governance, cultural protocols, and local authority. It recommends building an Indigenous data capability systemically over the long term and aligning infrastructure planning with Indigenous priorities. Similarly, the Indigenous Metadata Bundle Communique (TIMBC) highlights Indigenous epistemologies and cultural values. It views metadata as a cultural and political tool, capable of encoding rights, responsibilities, and collective benefit in technical environments. Incorporating cultural values in Indigenous data is also argued in the Enterprise Data Strategy 2024–27 (EDS) and Yurirka: Proppa Engagement with Aboriginal Peoples (YPEAP), ensuring cultural sensitivity and custodianship and recognising the right to data ownership and governance.

In addition to Indigenous data sovereignty and Indigenous community contribution, ethical use of Indigenous data is a critical concern. Learning lessons from the frameworks with the same concern is essential to inform frameworks aiming at building capacity for the use of data in SSR, particularly in Australia, where data related to indigenous people has an important and sensitive role in research. The Ethical Conduct in Research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples and Communities (ECR ATPC) includes six core values for ethical use of Indigenous data, including spirit and integrity, cultural continuity, equity, reciprocity, respect, and responsibility. It highlights intellectual property rights, gaining free, prior and informed consent from individuals and communities. It integrates Indigenous cultural protocols and methodologies into the research design, including co-conducting the research with community involvement; sharing and disseminating findings in accessible and consent-based ways; and ensuring follow-up and feedback with communities. The ethical use of Indigenous data is also discussed in Keeping Research on Track II (KRT II), produced with the Australian government. Similar to ECR ATPC, this framework also outlines core ethical values

such as spirit and integrity, cultural continuity, reciprocity, respect, equity, and responsibility, and guides researchers and communities through ethically sound research processes, including consent, cultural respect, benefit-sharing, and rights protection.

The review of Indigenous data governance frameworks demonstrates that integrating Indigenous perspectives is essential to building a nationally relevant and ethically grounded data skills framework. These documents consistently emphasise the need for Indigenous leadership, cultural authority, and community-led decision-making across all stages of the data lifecycle. Practical capabilities emerging from this literature include designing culturally responsive metadata, implementing ethical governance protocols, and supporting Indigenous-controlled infrastructure and stewardship. The CARE principles complement FAIR by embedding purpose, responsibility, and community benefit into data practice, while skills in consent, reciprocity, and co-developed access protocols are equally vital. Rather than treating these as specialist concerns, a robust skills framework must treat them as foundational competencies, ensuring that data work in Australia actively supports Indigenous sovereignty, advances ethical standards, and aligns with culturally safe and socially just practices.

Following the principles of Indigenous community involvement and self-determination outlined in the documents reviewed, it is clear that any section of the ADSSSF outlining necessary skills for working with Indigenous data will need to be co-designed with Indigenous researchers.

5 International frameworks

In addition to Australian data skills frameworks, we also reviewed some international frameworks to get insight into the global landscape of data skills. Due to the selection of criteria prioritising the English language, most of these frameworks are limited to the UK (15 frameworks) and the US (5 frameworks) (Figure 6). Each varies in scope, focus, aims and audience. As with the Australian selection, not all documents selected cover all data skills. Some focus only on research data management, others on open science, some on analytical methods, aiming to strengthen scholarly practices and some on

digital research infrastructure (e.g., SSNS DDR, UKDS DSF, and ESRC DDS). Others pay specific attention to building capacity for using data in governance, policy, evidence-based decision-making, and digital public service delivery (e.g., NDSF, QUKDSG, JNCC, UK-SCF and OECD FDTS and OECD SS). In addition to this, there are some frameworks that support public sector and workforce upskilling (e.g., IoA ACF, SF ICT, NCF DPHC, UN GWG, DALI DLF). While the competencies differ, most aim to build capacity for ethical, transparent use of data across different domains. Collectively, the documents cover the skills likely to be needed by Australian social sciences researchers.

Among the reviewed frameworks, a substantial group is focused on the effective use of data for research, particularly in social sciences, offering relevant insights for informing the development of ADSSSF. Most of these frameworks are UK-based, with a few contributions from the US, Canada, Germany, Singapore, and Ireland.

While we could not find Australian frameworks that are specifically designed for data-driven SSR, we have identified two such frameworks from the UK. These frameworks are the Scoping Study for National Strategy on Data-Driven Research Skills (SSNS DDRS) and the UKDS Data Skills Framework (UKDS DSF). They have a high capacity to inform work on the Australian framework due to their unique disciplinary focus and provision of structured training pathways.

Figure 6: The frequency of non-Australian reviewed frameworks by country

5.1 International data skills framework to inform research

Unlike the Australian frameworks reviewed, the SSNS DDRS contributes to building capacity within the UK social science research landscape by supporting data-driven research across the academic career life course, from post-PhD researchers to senior academics. It is particularly relevant for researchers working with both qualitative and quantitative data, including complex datasets. The report highlights the necessity of equipping social scientists at all career stages with adaptive and relevant skills that respond to rapid developments in data, technologies, and methodologies, such as AI, machine learning, and heterogeneous digital research methods. This framework supports training pathways that enable researchers to effectively engage with existing data infrastructure, including longitudinal studies, administrative data services, and doctoral training partnerships. This framework commits to building capacity for the use of data in SSR, stating in the introduction:

“Our vision is that social scientists at all career stages have the skills and capacity to maximise the value of large and complex data available for research purposes. Social scientists should be equipped with both the technical skills and the conceptual and

methodological understanding necessary to design and undertake data-driven research in efficient, reproducible, and methodologically responsible ways.”

SSNS DDR, 2023. P.2

The UKDS is another UK-based data skills framework supporting researchers across the social sciences, with a particular focus on large-scale surveys, censuses, and macro-level aggregate data. It is structured into twelve comprehensive skill domains, ranging from data access, management, and legal-ethical considerations to coding, AI-assisted analysis, and reproducibility, and provides a detailed guide to the competencies required for data-driven research. The framework plays a strategic and coordinating role across the broader training opportunities, supporting curriculum development, identifying gaps in provision, and guiding the design of flexible learning pathways. While the SSNS DDR outlines a strategic, life-course vision for data-driven research capacity across disciplines, the UKDS DSF complements it with a practical, modular structure centred on quantitative data skills essential for working with key social science datasets.

In contrast to the discipline-specific focus of the previous two works, another group of frameworks adopts a broader perspective on capacity building for research, such as the Data Science Body of Knowledge (DS-BoK, 2017) and the National Institute of Standards and Technology Research Data Framework (NIST RDF, 2023). These are not tailored to social science but offer substantial depth, methodological clarity, and practical guidance on tools and analytical techniques that are highly relevant to research domains.

DS-BoK focuses on data science education across academic institutions. It covers a wide range of knowledge, including business understanding, data engineering, data analytics, machine learning, research methods, and data science project management. It addresses multiple data types such as structured and unstructured data, and methods such as big data technologies, statistical analysis, predictive modelling, deep learning, cloud computing, and data ethics. The distinctive feature of this framework is its level of

attention to detail in explaining analytical tools and research methods. It includes detailed references to techniques like descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, regression analysis, hypothesis testing, Bayesian methods, and ANOVA. It also outlines methods relevant to data analytics and machine learning, including classification, clustering, association rule learning, decision trees, random forests, support vector machines, and neural networks. These are supported by introducing tools and technologies such as R, Python, Hadoop, Spark, and cloud platforms, demonstrating a high level of technical and methodological specificity. Although this document doesn't target social science, this level of detail is particularly important for building capacity for data-driven SSR, especially as it offers some training pathways.

Although both DS-BoK and NIST RDF support data-driven research, NIST RDF does so more directly by guiding effective research data management across disciplines using a lifecycle approach. NIST RDF is designed as a modular, non-prescriptive framework that helps institutions and individuals assess and improve their data management practices. It targets a wide range of stakeholders including researchers with emphasis on reproducibility, ethics, data governance, and lifecycle management. The distinctive feature of NIST RDF is its detailed mapping of data practices across six lifecycle stages, including envision, plan, generate/acquire, process/analyze, share/use/reuse, and preserve/discard. This lifecycle is complemented by 14 overarching themes, including ethics and CARE principles, metadata and provenance, data quality, reproducibility and FAIR principles, security and privacy, legal considerations, training and workforce development, and diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility. This structured mapping makes the framework particularly useful for researchers aiming to enhance open, ethical, and sustainable data practices³⁰. While it acknowledges the significance of qualitative data, it does not offer specific methods for working with them alone or within mixed methods designs, which may limit direct application in some social science contexts.

³⁰ The Turing Way Institute also offers useful insight <https://book.the-turing-way.org/>

Another major theme in this group is the development of institutional-level capability models, such as the Jisc Building Digital Capabilities Framework (BDCF) and the Researcher Role Profile: Six Elements of Digital Capabilities (RRP SEDC). These frameworks emphasise digital literacy for workforce readiness and role-based self-assessment rather than methodological or analytic training. While they do not offer detailed guidance on data analysis, they are valuable for supporting research environments by strengthening the necessary digital competencies for responsible and sustainable data use. Jisc BDCF, in particular, supports education and professional development, specifically focusing on enhancing digital skills. It addresses a wide range of digital skills, including the use of generative AI, with a focus on inclusive, ethical, and sustainable practices. It includes data literacy as a core element, covering data management, visualisation, interpretation, security, and ethics, but does not prescribe specific methods for analysis. Its strength lies in its flexible structure with role-adaptable profiles and self-assessment tools. The RRP SEDC also targets post-compulsory education and research, outlining six capability areas including ICT proficiency, information, media, data literacy, digital creation, communication and collaboration, digital learning and teaching, and digital identity. It includes relevant skills such as data management, coding, spreadsheet use, media production, and critical evaluation, though it does not provide instructional content. Among these two frameworks, the Jisc BDCF offers more detailed skill levels, making it more actionable for training design and workforce development.

Reviewing this group of international frameworks highlights the diversity of approaches to support data-driven research and education and support workforce upskilling, with each demonstrating unique strengths for the development of the ADSSSF. The UK-based frameworks (SSNS DDR and UKDS DSF) stand out for their specific focus on SSR, offering structured, career-spanning training pathways. Broader frameworks like DS-BoK and NIST RDaF provide methodological and technical guidance across disciplines. Institutional capability frameworks such as Jisc BDCF and RRP SEDC, while not analytically focused, strengthen digital data literacy and self-assessment capacity across research roles and education. Reviewing these frameworks offers

complementary models to inform a comprehensive, flexible, and interdisciplinary approach to advancing data science capabilities in the Australian research sector.

5.2 International data skills framework to inform policy making and industry

Unlike the research-focused frameworks discussed above, the frameworks reviewed in this section were developed primarily to inform policy, decision-making, workforce upskilling, and sector-wide digital capability development. They are included selectively in this review because they offer lessons not fully covered by the research-focused frameworks, particularly in relation to capability maturity, workforce planning, proficiency levels, transferable skills, training design, and the organisational conditions required to support data use at scale. These issues are relevant to the ADSSSF because the framework is intended not only to identify the data skills needed by social science researchers but also to support future training opportunities, institutional adoption, and cross-sector application. For this reason, this section focuses only on elements of these frameworks that provide additional value for developing a practical, implementable, and sustainable data skills framework for Australian social science research.

Within this group, some frameworks focus on digital literacy for policy planning. While they reference data skills, they rarely engage deeply with methods. One example is the 2021 US National Digital Skills Framework (NDSF), which includes foundational to advanced digital competencies relevant across sectors, such as communication, information handling, device use, problem-solving, and digital citizenship. It categorises skills under five broad areas and includes detailed examples of tasks and behaviours at four proficiency. This task-based approach is an effective way to enhance the efficiency of the framework, not only in policy-making, but also those targeting SSR.

Another similar approach to policy and decision-making is the Quantifying the UK Data Skills Gap (QUKDSG). It assesses the extent and nature of data skills shortages in the UK workforce. It focuses on data literacy and data analysis skills across sectors and job roles and examines demand, supply, and barriers to training. The report combines quantitative surveys of employers, workers, and students with an analysis of job advertisements using labour market analytics and includes qualitative interviews with

key stakeholders. These methods identify the types of data skills that the current UK job market requires and the gaps between workforce capabilities and employer needs.

The report is useful for this review because it identifies concrete data skills that are in demand across the UK labour market, including information management, data communication, data literacy, data ethics, database management, analysis skills, data visualisation, data processing, programming, advanced statistics, machine learning, and knowledge of emerging technologies. It therefore provides a useful external reference point for ADSSSF, not as a direct model for social science research, but as evidence of the broader data capabilities that researchers may increasingly need when working across academic, government, industry, and policy settings. This approach can help ADSSSF identify which transferable skills should be considered alongside research-specific competencies and can support the development of more focused training opportunities.

OECD Skills Strategy (OECD SS) is also a policy-centred framework, with a more general and cross-sector approach than the previous two (QUKDSG and NDSF). It prioritises three key skills, including foundational cognitive skills such as literacy and numeracy, social and emotional skills like resilience and the ability to work with others, and transferable skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability. Its main audience is national governments and policymakers, particularly those engaged in education, labour markets, economic development, industry, and public governance. The framework promotes a lifelong learning approach to developing relevant skills, supports their effective use in work and society, and highlights the importance of whole-of-government coordination, stakeholder participation, integrated information systems, and aligned financing to strengthen skills system governance. It emphasises lifelong and adaptable skill development and offers a useful model to create responsive training opportunities for SSR.

Another similar approach to the OECD SS, NDSF, and QUKDSG, is Digital Skills for All Non-IT Roles Across Multiple Industries (DS ANRMI), which focuses on mapping current and future digital and data skill needs across sectors in Ireland to inform policy, training, and organisational readiness. This framework identifies core transferable skills,

such as data input, analysis, visualisation, and digital problem-solving, and supports evidence-informed decisions for national upskilling, lifelong learning, and education reform. It includes tool examples in nine groups including Data analysis tools (Excel, SAS, Alteryx, Minitab, Informa), Data visualisation tools (Power BI, Tableau, Qlik, Looker, Diver), Project management tools (Jira, Trello, Microsoft Project, Kanban), Automation tools (Nintex, Power Automate, SAP Fiori, UI Path, VB Apps), Communication and collaboration tools (Microsoft 365, Google Suite, Slack, WebEx, Zoom), Database management tools (MySQL, Oracle, Azure Databricks, Cloudera, Spreadsheet Server), Programming and simulation tools (Python, R, SQL, C/C++, JavaScript, MATLAB, Simio, Sim Center Star CCM+, Deform), Computer-aided design (CAD) tools (AutoCAD, CREO, SolidWorks, Siemens NX, Visio), ERP and CRM tools (SAP, Salesforce, Oracle JD Edwards EnterpriseOne, Workday, HubSpot, WebOps, 6Sense). Like QUKDSG, it uses a mix of surveys, focus groups, and expert input to identify workforce capabilities and gaps, making it a reference for developing ADSSSF.

In contrast to broader workforce or education-focused frameworks, the Skills and Competency Framework (UK SCF) focused on strengthening the UK's infrastructure data and national digital twin. It takes a technically specific and infrastructure-oriented approach to data skills for decision making. It has been developed to support the adoption of information management frameworks across the UK to inform built environment policies; however, many of the digital skills discussed in this framework can be applied to ADSSSF. For instance, it outlines digital skills such as data fundamentals, analytics and intelligence, data modelling, lifecycle assurance, security and ethics, and user experience design. These skills are defined through four levels of competency, each with practical indicators. The framework was informed by stakeholder workshops and interviews, which helped identify existing skills gaps and priorities at both organisational and national levels. Although it does not provide training content, it offers guidance for designing targeted training pathways, assessing gaps, and implementing capability-building programmes. It also highlights societal and ethical dimensions of data and promotes digital literacy as a national challenge that extends beyond technical implementation.

The OECD framework: digital talent and skills in the public sector (OECD FDTs) is also a sector-specific framework that aims to inform how government institutions are structured and how their workplace cultures operate, to support digital transformation. While the main audience of this framework is government institutions, digital transformation is equally a concern in SSR. Unlike technical frameworks, such as the UK SCF, the OECD FDTs draws on qualitative data from country case studies, expert consultations, and policy analysis. It is structured around three principles, including enabling environment, skills needed, and talent management. It offers conceptual and practical guidance through illustrative roles, skill clusters, and working methods such as co-design, user research, and agile delivery. Its emphasis is on building the institutional conditions, leadership capacity, and workforce strategies needed to embed digital transformation across the public sector.

Other frameworks aim to build capacity for using data in the public sector. For instance, the Digital, Data and Technology (DDaT) Playbook originated in the UK government and aims to improve the sourcing, contracting, and management of digital, data, and technology projects to deliver secure, sustainable, and user-centred public services. It provides detailed, process-oriented guidance tailored for policymakers, procurement professionals, digital teams, and project managers. It covers outcome-based contracting, delivery models, technology readiness assessments, open standards, cybersecurity risk assessment, and the use of AI/Machine Learning. It also outlines governance expectations, skills requirements, and commercial strategies. These values are not only useful in the public sector but also for those social science researchers who aim to conduct data-driven studies.

The Data Capability Framework (DCF) is also a policy-focused approach to enhance data use and capability in the public sector (Similar to DDaT and OECD FDTs). Data use is a main theme in SSR, making these frameworks good examples for developing ADSSSF to inform SSR. DCF targets public sector workers at different levels and supports institutional transformation by embedding data-informed decision-making into workforce structures and leadership practices. It outlines a detailed capability matrix in four groups, including data management, data analysis, data-informed decision-making, and leadership, each with four proficiency levels. These levels are described through

expected outputs to guide professional development, recruitment, and organisational planning. While the framework remains general in its approach to data skills, it emphasises transferable competencies such as ethical data handling, interpreting data in context, and using evidence in policy processes.

Another group of frameworks in this group focus on particular policy areas and are strong examples because they go beyond general guidance to specify how to do things and what tools and skills are needed. For example, the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC) competency framework aims to support the development of a UK-wide evidence framework for nature-based solutions (NbS) by identifying data needs, relevant skills, and methods for monitoring and evaluating NbS outcomes. It targets policymakers, practitioners, environmental agencies, and researchers involved in implementing or assessing NbS. Although the focus of this framework is environmental sustainability, it is a good example for ADSSSF with the level of detail it provides in terms of skills and methods. It uses methods such as literature review, expert consultation, and stakeholder workshops to develop a monitoring and evaluation framework. The included quantitative data of ecological indicators, remote sensing outputs, and socioeconomic statistics, while qualitative data involves community perceptions, lived experiences, and cultural values. It defines seven key themes, such as data governance, analysis, modelling, and visualisation, each articulated across beginner to expert levels. Originally developed for environmental roles, it is notable for its tool-specific guidance, including Python, R, SQL, GIS, QGIS, and ENVI, as well as its inclusion of diverse data types like spatial, imagery, and sensor data. This framework addresses both technical and organisational competencies, making it adaptable for use in ADSSSF.

5.3 International frameworks for professional development in data science and analytics

This third major theme in the global practices is those primarily developed to guide data science and analytics roles in professional or technical contexts, often without focusing on specific fields. They provide models for defining career pathways, mapping skills across job roles, and linking capabilities with practical tasks and technologies.

Some frameworks in this group support data professionals and analysts through structured progression and task-based skill development. For instance, the Institute of Analytics Analyst Competency Framework (IoA ACF) defines skill levels for data analysts across different career stages, while targeting early-career and mid-career professionals, and those retraining. It outlines a clear developmental pathway across five levels and covers technical proficiencies such as R and Python, working with structured and unstructured data, big data tools, and ethical decision-making, while also recognising interdisciplinary applications and leadership. This is adaptable to the ADSSSF to enhance the technical literacy of social science researchers with different levels of proficiency. IoA ACF supports end-to-end analytics processes, including problem identification, data acquisition, analysis, interpretation, and evaluation. It embeds key competencies such as coding, data manipulation, visual storytelling, ethics, communication, governance, and leadership. The framework also supports up to 35 hours of structured training per year, including ethical and interdisciplinary competencies throughout. A similar approach with potential to inform ADSSSF in terms of task-based skill development is the Data Skills Framework- DSF Ireland Digital Skillnet.

The Skills Framework for ICT (SF ICT), developed in Singapore, offers one of the most granular structures for data science roles. It was primarily designed for data scientists but has a contextual approach to skills and defines 104 job roles across 7 tracks (e.g., data analyst, data engineer, data scientist/AI scientist, AI/ML engineer, and chief data/AI office) and 32 sub-tracks, each with detailed role descriptions, required skills, tasks, and proficiency levels. The framework covers domains such as data and artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, infrastructure, software and applications, strategy and governance, and operations and support. For each job role, it includes applied methods such as data extraction, statistical analysis, machine learning model development, model evaluation, simulation, and data visualisation, particularly within data-related roles. It can be a guide for ADSSSF by listing what methods for each skill need to be learnt for each role and level of data literacy. For example, for a social science researcher at the foundational level, it might include modules on data cleaning,

visualisation tools, basic statistics, and reporting software. These learning roadmaps can support curriculum development and individual upskilling.

Another prominent example is the National Competency Framework for Data Professionals in Health and Care (NCF DPHC) from the UK, which aims to professionalise those who work in the data workforce, particularly in the health and social care sectors. Its target group includes data professionals working in or aspiring to roles in data analysis, data engineering, and data science within health and social care settings, across levels from junior analysts to directors. On page four in the document, they note:

“This framework is designed to map directly to DDaT but with the luxury of being able to be more specific for health and social care Data occupations”

NCF DPHC, P.4

NCF DPHC covers methods such as descriptive, predictive, prescriptive, evaluative analytics, data modelling, machine learning, metadata management, automation, and communication for different levels (L1 to L5 for Data Analysis; L1 to L4 for Data Engineering and Data Science). NCF DPHC also includes additional skill areas to reflect expertise in more specific methods, such as geospatial analysis or hypothesis testing. These are intended to adapt the core competencies to particular roles or settings, such as public health, mental health, or cancer services. This role- and setting-sensitive approach is useful for ADSSSF because it shows how a general skills framework can retain a shared structure while allowing particular research areas, data types, and methodological needs within social science to be represented through more specialised skill extensions.

Some of these frameworks are specifically focused on statistical systems and big data, a similar approach to some of the reviewed Australian frameworks. While technological advancements over the past few years have facilitated data collection and the availability of administrative and big data in Australia for research purposes, it is crucial for social science researchers to ensure the ability to work with big data and

administrative data to address their complex research questions. One useful example is the UN Global Working Group on Big Data for Official Statistics Competency Framework (UN GWG) that provides a skills architecture designed for national statistical offices but applicable more broadly. The framework identified gaps in areas such as machine learning, programming, ethics and privacy in data use, data integration and management, and the ability to translate data into actionable insights. It also highlights soft skills like communication, storytelling, and adaptability, suggesting that data professionals may need development in these areas alongside technical expertise. The framework lists functional tasks such as data acquisition, cleaning, integration, and dissemination. In terms of training, it doesn't offer a fixed or mandatory curriculum, training pathway, but it refers to examples such as the Data Science Academy to illustrate how skill progression and role-based development (e.g. for data engineers or analysts) can be supported. Such implementation guidance is essential for translating national frameworks into effective practice across sectors.

5.4 What we learnt from the review of international data skills frameworks

The reviewed international frameworks show a shared commitment to strengthening data capability through interdisciplinary capacity building, ethical awareness, role-based flexibility, and structured skill development. However, they vary significantly in scope, methodological depth, intended audience, and direct relevance to social science research. Some frameworks are designed specifically to support data-driven research, while others focus on public sector capability, workforce upskilling, policy decision-making, or professional data science and analytics roles.

The UK-based social science research frameworks, particularly SSNS DDR, UKDS DSF, and ESRC DDS, are the most directly relevant to ADSSSF because they explicitly address the skills required for data-driven social science research. They provide useful models for linking technical, conceptual, methodological, and ethical competencies with training pathways and research infrastructure, including longitudinal studies, administrative data systems, and large-scale survey data. These frameworks demonstrate the value of designing a data skills framework around the actual conditions

of social science research rather than treating data skills as generic technical competencies.

At the same time, the broader international policy, workforce, and professional frameworks also offer useful lessons for ADSSSF. Although they are not designed specifically for social science researchers, they show how data skills can be translated into proficiency levels, role profiles, capability matrices, task-based competencies, workforce planning tools, and training strategies. These features are important for ADSSSF because the framework is intended not only to identify relevant data skills, but also to support training design, institutional adoption, and long-term capacity building across the Australian social science research sector.

A notable limitation across many of the reviewed frameworks is their insufficient attention to qualitative and mixed-methods research. Many frameworks give greater attention to quantitative, technical, administrative, or computational data practices, while offering less guidance on how qualitative data, interpretive methods, participatory research, and mixed-methods designs fit within data skills development. This is a significant consideration for ADSSSF, given the methodological diversity of social science research.

The international review suggests that ADSSSF should draw most directly on the UK social science research frameworks, while selectively adapting useful design principles from broader policy, workforce, and professional frameworks. A strong Australian framework should therefore combine social science relevance with practical implementability. It should accommodate foundational data literacy, methodological diversity, ethical and responsible data use, role-based specialisations, training pathways, and sustainable support mechanisms for researchers and research infrastructure professionals.

6 Research Software Engineering in Social Science Research

In the rapidly evolving technological landscape, close collaboration between software engineers and researchers is increasingly essential. Lack of shared understanding

between software engineers and researchers can hinder the effective implementation of digital tools and methods in research. RSE has emerged to bridge this gap; however, its role in supporting SSR remains fragmented. This fragmentation stems partly from the fact that RSE frameworks are typically developed in isolation from social science data skills frameworks and theories, leading to a lack of shared understanding between SSR and RSE about research needs and the skills required to meet these needs.

RSEs are broadly defined as professionals who combine software engineering expertise with a deep understanding of the research process. Their responsibilities span the computational lifecycle of research, including software development, reproducibility, and sustainability. Foundational competencies include software design, version control, documentation, and contributions to reproducible research, as identified in the “Research software engineering” skill family in DRCSF. Goth et al. (2023)³¹ describe RSEs as hybrid professionals who require coding skills, knowledge of the research cycle, and interdisciplinary communication abilities. They propose a competency framework to guide training and career development, stressing the importance of RSEs in ensuring high-quality, ethical, and reproducible research.

Definitions of RSEs vary across contexts, a factor that enhances the potential to define approaches tailored to SSR contexts. Sochat ³²et al. (2022) argue that the meaning of RSE depends on who uses the term and in what kind of research. Rather than enforcing a single definition, they propose the Research Software Encyclopedia as a flexible framework to evaluate software’s research relevance, offering a shared taxonomy and tools to support software maintenance and collaboration across disciplines.

³¹ Goth, F., Alves, R., Braun, M., Castro, L. J., Chourdakis, G., Christ, S., ... & Wittke, S. (2023). Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of a Research Software Engineer. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2311.11457*.

³² Sochat, V., May, N., Cosden, I., Martinez-Ortiz, C., & Bartholomew, S. (2022). The Research Software Encyclopedia: a community framework to define research software. *Journal of Open Research Software*.

The US RSE community further highlights the emergence of RSE as a distinct career path, with emphasis on leadership, creativity, interdisciplinary collaboration, and the need for community-building, professional recognition, and tailored training. Similarly, Baxter et al. (2012)³³ emphasise that RSEs differ from contract programmers by combining domain knowledge with engineering expertise. They play a vital intellectual role in research and are often co-authors. Yet, academia often lacks career pathways, institutional recognition, and funding for RSEs, requiring cultural and structural change at the national level.

Several documents position RSEs as methodologically significant, essential to research transparency, reuse, and validation. Heroux (2022)³⁴ advocates for research software itself to become a subject of scientific inquiry through experimentation and analysis of its technical and social dimensions. Felderer et al. (2025)³⁵ distinguish research software from commercial software by its complexity, lack of standardised processes, and context-specific requirements. They call for international collaboration, improved tools, training, and the formal establishment of RSE research as a field.

Benthall et al. (2020)³⁶ believe that RSE should be recognised as a core scholarly method in SSR. They add that RSE should include skills, such as reproducible modelling, infrastructure maintenance, and interactive dissemination. These skills are essential for transparency, reuse, and interdisciplinary collaboration with SRE. The paper proposes integrating RSE training into graduate curricula and adopting an apprenticeship model to treat software development as legitimate academic work, not just technical support.

³³ Baxter, R., Hong, N. C., Gorissen, D., Hetherington, J., & Todorov, I. (2012, September). The research software engineer. In *Digital research 2012*.

³⁴ Heroux, M. A. (2023). Research software science: Expanding the impact of research software engineering. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 24(6), 22-27.

³⁵ Felderer, M., Goedicke, M., Grunske, L., Hasselbring, W., Lamprecht, A. L., & Rumpe, B. (2025). Investigating research software engineering: Toward RSE research. *Communications of the ACM*, 68(2), 20-23.

³⁶ Benthall, S., Seth, M., Agarwal, M., Calloway, C., Niederhut, D., & Shupe, D. (2020). Software Engineering as Research Method: Aligning Roles in Econ-ARK. In *SciPy* (pp. 156-161).

For a transparent collaboration of SRE and SSR, the FAIR principles have been extended to address issues of discoverability and reproducibility. Chue Hong et al. (2022)³⁷ and Barker et al. (2022)³⁸ articulate these principles as essential for software sustainability. Martinez (2023) reiterates that software's executability and evolving nature require it to be treated as a distinct scholarly output, with FAIR as an aspirational rather than binary standard. Bannert (2024)³⁹ further supports this by offering best practices in software engineering for researchers, including version control, modular design, and reproducibility, with practical examples in R.

In terms of institutional positioning, some argue for formal recognition of the RSE role in academia, integrated into open science and data stewardship initiatives. Beavan et al. (2025)⁴⁰, focusing on arts and humanities, emphasise the significance of a national directory of RSEs, structured training, an incubator for tool development, and continuous evaluation. These frameworks not only advocate for the profession but also provide templates for embedding RSEs into research, grants, supervisory roles, and infrastructure teams.

From a methodological perspective, Runeson and Höst (2009)⁴¹ provide guidance on using case studies in software engineering to investigate real-world, complex phenomena, which can be highly useful for social science contexts. Lorey et al. (2022)⁴² identify the reason behind the separation of RSE and SSR as the underuse of social

³⁷ Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F. E., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., & Martinez, P. A. (2022). FAIR principles for research software (FAIR4RS principles). *Zenodo*.

³⁸ Barker, M., Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez-Ortiz, C., Psomopoulos, F., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., & Martinez, P. A. (2022). Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 622.

³⁹ Bannert, M. (2024). *Research Software Engineering: A Guide to the Open Source Ecosystem*. CRC Press.

⁴⁰ Beavan, D., Piza, A., Gillespie, S., Buchuck-Wilsenach, C., Bailey-ross, C., Bickford, J., Chalstrey, E., Chester-Kadwell, M., Hong, N. P. C., & Ciula, A. (2025). Towards a National Research Software Engineering Capability in Arts and Humanities Research: a Roadmap.

⁴¹ Runeson, P., & Höst, M. (2009). Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering. *Empirical software engineering*, 14, 131-164.

⁴² Lorey, T., Ralph, P., & Felderer, M. (2022). Social science theories in software engineering research. Proceedings of the 44th International Conference on Software Engineering,

science theories in software engineering, noting that only 2% of SE papers substantially engage with such theories. Most rely on psychology and management, often for study design rather than theory-building.

Addressing these gaps, Jackson (2013)⁴³ presents a framework for using software modelling in interdisciplinary SSR. Treating simulation as a third pillar alongside theory and empiricism, the framework supports hypothesis testing, scenario analysis, and uncertainty management. It blends agile methods, abstract state machines, and collaborative tools to support iterative and reproducible modelling. Applications in criminology, public health, and urban studies show its potential in enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration and theory development.

This perspective treats software as a core research product requiring dedicated stewardship throughout its lifecycle. This view is largely absent from many Australian reviewed frameworks, where software is often framed as a support function. Integrating RSE considerations into the ADSSSF would help shift this view by recognising software development as scholarly work in its own right.

Finally, documents that move beyond abstract advocacy to outline concrete ways to embed RSEs within academic systems are particularly valuable. These include models for integrating RSEs into institutional roles, supervisory teams, and funding structures. For the ADSSSF, this suggests a need to include not only training modules but also organisational guidelines and role models to ensure that RSEs are fully utilised rather than marginalised within the social sciences.

In this review, we observed a lack of guidance on software stewardship across the research lifecycle. In SSR, this stewardship cannot be treated as a purely technical matter. It needs to be informed by theoretical, methodological, and disciplinary knowledge, because software tools shape how research questions are operationalised, how data are processed, and how findings are produced and interpreted. This is a key point where SSR and RSE intersect, and where closer collaboration is needed. The

⁴³ Jackson, P. J. (2013). A framework for software modelling in social science research.

disconnection between SSR and RSE can negatively affect the sustainability of data skills for research purposes, as well as the sustainability, transparency, and reusability of the digital research outputs that result from those skills. Hartmann and Sprenger (2011)⁴⁴ refer to this problem as the “Toolbox View”, where computational tools are deployed without sufficient attention to their theoretical underpinnings, highlighting the need for a more context-sensitive approach.

The collaboration challenge also stems from RSE being an emerging field that is still addressing fundamental institutional positioning issues. The capacity to develop discipline-specific frameworks and stronger theoretical integration requires RSE to establish clearer academic legitimacy and recognition in the broader research ecosystem. Addressing these foundational challenges would enable more sophisticated integration with disciplines such as SSR. Initiatives such as ongoing training are useful for addressing skill gaps through hands-on, peer-led learning. Hampton et al. (2017)⁴⁵ argue that these programmes are effective in fostering core technical fluency, reproducibility, and collaboration, qualities that could be adapted to meet the distinct needs of social science researchers.

7 Summary

This review examined how data skills, digital research capabilities, Indigenous data governance, and Research Software Engineering are conceptualised across Australian and international frameworks, guidelines, grey literature, and academic sources. The purpose of the review was to identify models, gaps, and transferable design principles that can inform the development of the Australian Data Skills for Social Sciences

⁴⁴ Hartmann, Stephan, and Jan Sprenger. "Mathematics and statistics in the social sciences." *The SAGE handbook of the philosophy of social sciences* (2011): 594-612.

⁴⁵ Hampton, S. E., Jones, M. B., Wasser, L. A., Schildhauer, M. P., Supp, S. R., Brun, J., Hernandez, R. R., Boettiger, C., Collins, S. L., & Gross, L. J. (2017). Skills and knowledge for data-intensive environmental research. *BioScience*, 67(6), 546-557.

Framework (ADSSSF). In total, 159 documents were reviewed, including Australian frameworks and guidelines, international data skills frameworks, Indigenous data governance documents, and Research Software Engineering sources.

The review shows that data capability is increasingly recognised as essential across research, government, industry, health, education, and public sector settings. Many of the reviewed documents emphasise data governance, privacy, security, ethical data use, data management, technical competency, AI-related risk, and workforce capability development. However, their relevance to social science research varies considerably. Most Australian frameworks are not designed specifically for social science researchers, and many focus instead on public sector data governance, digital transformation, health data, AI assurance, spatial data infrastructure, or professional data science roles. While these documents provide useful lessons, they do not fully address the methodological, interpretive, ethical, and mixed-methods needs of social science research.

A key finding is that Australia currently lacks a dedicated data skills framework designed for social science researchers. Some Australian frameworks, particularly the ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework, provide valuable models for role-based skills, proficiency levels, research infrastructure planning, and links between skills and concrete tasks. Other frameworks offer useful insights into data governance, administrative data, spatial data, AI ethics, metadata, privacy, and institutional capability. Nevertheless, these contributions remain dispersed across different sectors and are not organised around the specific needs of social science research.

The international review partly addresses this gap. UK-based social science research frameworks, particularly SSNS DDR, UKDS DSF, and ESRC DDS, are especially relevant because they directly consider the skills required for data-driven social science research, including links to training pathways and research infrastructure such as longitudinal studies, administrative data systems, and large-scale survey data. Broader policy, workforce, and professional frameworks are less directly aligned with SSR, but still offer useful design principles for ADSSSF, including proficiency levels, role profiles, task-based competencies, workforce planning, capability matrices, and implementation-oriented training models. These elements are important because ADSSSF needs to be

both conceptually relevant to social science and practically usable for training design, institutional adoption, and long-term capacity building.

The review also highlights two areas that are often treated separately from mainstream data skills frameworks but are essential for ADSSSF. First, Indigenous data governance frameworks demonstrate that data skills in the Australian context must be grounded in Indigenous data sovereignty, community authority, cultural protocols, ethical governance, reciprocity, and the CARE principles. These should not be treated as specialist or optional concerns, but as foundational to responsible data practice in Australia. Any ADSSSF component addressing Indigenous data should therefore be co-designed with Indigenous researchers and communities.

Second, the review of Research Software Engineering shows that software, code, computational workflows, and digital tools should not be treated merely as technical support functions. In data-driven social science, they can shape how research questions are operationalised, how data are processed, and how findings are produced, interpreted, reproduced, and shared. This points to the need for software stewardship across the research lifecycle, informed by both technical expertise and social science theory. Integrating RSE into ADSSSF would help recognise software development, reproducibility, documentation, sustainability, and collaboration with RSEs as part of responsible and rigorous social science research.

Overall, this review provides a foundation for developing ADSSSF as a nationally relevant, social science-focused, and implementation-oriented framework. The framework should identify the specific data skills required by social science researchers while also supporting training pathways, role-based guidance, ethical and responsible data use, Indigenous data governance, mixed-methods capability, AI literacy, spatial and administrative data skills, software stewardship, and collaboration with research infrastructure professionals. In doing so, ADSSSF can help build more coherent, inclusive, reproducible, and sustainable data practices across the Australian social science research sector.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Tables outlining reviewed frameworks

Table 1 Australian frameworks and guidelines

URL	Framework	Year	Producer
https://ardc.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/The-pathway-towards-an-ARDC-DDR.pdf	ARDC Digital Research Capabilities and Skills Framework	2021	ARDC
https://zenodo.org/records/14188836	ARDC Digital Research Capabilities & Skills Framework: The Framework and Its Components	2024	ARDC
https://www.apsc.gov.au/sites/default/files/202211/APS%20Data%20Capability%20Framework%20%28final%29_0.pdf	APS Data Capability Framework Production release	2022	Australian Public Service (APS) Data Professional Stream
https://www.naa.gov.au/informationmanagement/professional-development-and-support/capability-skills-and-professional-development/information-management-and-data-capabilities	National Archives of Australia (NAA) - Information Management and Data Capabilities	2021	National Archives of Australia
https://www.datacommissioner.gov.au/sites/default/files/2022-08/foundational-four.pdf	The Foundational Four	2020	Office of the National Data Commissioner

https://wadsih.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/WADSIH-Data-Science-Competency-Framework-2021-1-1.pdf	WADSIH Data Science Competency Framework	2021	WA Data Science Innovation Hub
https://uploadsssl.webflow.com/5cd23e823ab9b1f01f815a54/5d0076903a1e4f6bb45ea50b_Data%20Science%20Competency%20Framework.pdf	Data science competency framework	2017	Defence-focused Cooperative Research Centre
https://www.dewr.gov.au/foundation-skills-your-future-program/resources/digital-literacy-skills-framework	Digital Literacy Skills Framework	2021	Department of Employment, Skills, Small and Family Business
https://www.dataanddigital.gov.au/sites/default/files/2023-12/Data%20and%20Digital%20Government%20Strategy%20v1.0.pdf	Data and Digital Government Strategy	2023	Department of Finance and Digital Transformation Agency
https://www.niaa.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/2024-05/framework-governance-indigenous-data.pdf	Framework for Governance of Indigenous Data	2024	Australian Public Service –
https://research.usq.edu.au/download/613af3d1aa53d62b4079e0b7a74a5504dcb79feb7bc2a3eb5e922f5a89145cc/2985848/Research%20Data%20Management%20Framework%20for%20Institutions_web.pdf	Research Data Management Framework for Institutions	2023	Higher Education and Research Sector
https://micro.org.au/documents/research-data-management-policy-framework-v1-0/	Research Data Management Policy Framework	2021	Research Infrastructure Sector

https://www.health.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/2021/12/framework-to-guide-the-secondary-use-of-my-health-record-system-data.pdf	Framework to guide the secondary use of My Health Record system data	2018	Australian Government – Department of Health
https://www.finance.gov.au/sites/default/files/2022-10/australian-data-strategy.pdf	Australian Data Strategy	2022	Australian Government – Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet (PM&C)
https://www.austlii.edu.au/cgi-bin/viewdb/au/legis/cth/consol_act/daata2022312/	Data Availability and Transparency Act	2022	Australian Government – Office of the Parliamentary Counsel
https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/completed/data-access/data-availability-use-government-response.pdf	Australian Government Response to Data Availability and Use Inquiry	2018	Australian Government – Department of the Prime Minister and Cabinet (PM&C), 2018
https://www.wgea.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/WGEA%20-%20Data%20Governance%20Framework.pdf	Data Governance Framework Workplace Gender Equality Agency	2020	Australian Government – Workplace Gender Equality Agency (WGEA)
https://www.csiro.au/en/research/technology-space/cyber/a-framework-for-data-de-identification	De-Identification Decision-Making Framework	2017	Australian Government, Developed jointly by CSIRO
https://www.dewr.gov.au/skills-reform/resources/australian-digital-capability-framework	Australian Digital Capability Framework	2022	Australian Government, Department of Employment and Workplace Relations
https://www.acs.org.au/insightsandpublications/reports-publications/data-sharing-frameworks.html	ACS Data Sharing Framework	2017	Australian Computer Society (ACS)

https://www.acma.gov.au/sites/default/files/2022-05/Data%20strategy%20and%20governance%20framework.pdf	ACMA Data Strategy and Governance Framework	2022	Australian Government, Australian Communications and Media Authority (ACMA)
https://www.safetyandquality.gov.au/publications-and-resources/resource-library/acsqhc-data-governance-framework	ACSQHC Data Governance Framework	2023	Australian Government, Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Health Care
https://www.anzlic.gov.au/sites/default/files/files/one_australian_and_new_zealand_foundation_spatial_data_framework_booklet.doc	Australian and New Zealand Foundation Spatial Data Framework	2014	ANZLIC – the Spatial Information Council
https://www.aihw.gov.au/getmedia/1c95574c-ac07-4126-8b7c-31eb29d9b381/oos318_attachment-1.pdf.aspx	Australian Health Performance Framework	2017	Australian Health Ministers' Advisory Council (AHMAC),
https://www.dewr.gov.au/about-department/resources/dewr-data-strategy-2024-2027	Department of Employment and Workplace Relations Data Strategy	2024	Australian Government – Department of Employment and Workplace Relations
https://nwmpnh.org.au/wpcontent/uploads/2024/03/NWMPH-N-Data-Governance-Framework-FINAL.pdf	NWMPHN Data Governance Framework	2024	Northwestern Melbourne Primary Health Network
https://www.oaic.gov.au/about-the-OAIC/our-corporate-information/plans-policies-and-procedures/oaic-data-strategy	OAIC Data Strategy	2023	Australian Government

https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/data-strategy-2021-2024/2-governance-optimize-our-data-governance-and-management	Data Strategy 2021–2024	2021	Australian Government – Department of Industry, Science, Energy and Resources (DISER)
https://www.hostingcertification.gov.au/framework	Hosting Certification Framework	2021	Australian Government – Digital Transformation Agency (DTA)
https://www.act.gov.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0011/2543645/ACT-Data-Governance-and-Management-Framework.pdf	ACT Data Governance and Management Framework	2020	ACT Government
https://data.nsw.gov.au/sites/default/files/inline-files/IDMF-V3-small_0.pdf	NSW Infrastructure Data Management Framework	2019	NSW Government – Department of Customer Service
https://data.nsw.gov.au/nsw-government-data-strategy	NSW Government Data Strategy	2021	NSW Government – Data Analytics Centre
https://rasd.org.au/pdf-html/who-manages-this-framework.html	National Framework for the Sharing of Restricted Access Species Data in Australia	2023	Coordinated by the Atlas of Living Australia (ALA) and CSIRO
https://www.treasury.sa.gov.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0007/1066417/Open-Data-Process-Guide.pdf	Open Data Process Guide	2014	South Australian Government – Office of the Chief Information Officer (OCIO)
https://www.governanceinstitute.com.au/app/uploads/2023/12/data-governance-report-2023.pdf#page=20.05	Data Governance in Australia	2023	Governance Institute of Australia, in partnership with Macquarie University's DataX Research Centre and CSIRO's National AI Centre

https://www.aihw.gov.au/getmedia/3117bc9c-46ee-4891-a423-2ec0d66e12e7/aihw-data-governance-framework-2022.pdf.aspx#page=8.28	AIHW Data Governance Framework	2022	Australian Government – Australian Institute of Health and Welfare
https://www.education.gov.au/download/4977/abs-capacity-contribute-data-quality-framework/7445/document/pdf	Data Quality Framework for the Australian Government's Direct Measure of Income	2020	Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS), commissioned by the Department of Education, Skills and Employment
https://www.wa.gov.au/system/files/2024-03/imf-for-wa-v2.pdf	Information Management Framework for Western Australia	2024	Government of Western Australia
https://www.adelaide.edu.au/melt/ua/media/51/rsd-framework.pdf	Research Skill Development Framework		The University of Adelaide
https://www.canberra.edu.au/uc-research/graduate-research/current-research-students/development/skills-framework/RDSF-Guide.pdf#page=8.71	QUADRANT 2 research management		University of Canberra
https://www.naturalhazards.com.au/sites/default/files/2022-05/NatHazResAus%20Data%20Management%20Framework.pdf	Natural Hazards Research Australia Data Management Framework	2022	Natural Hazards Research Australia
https://ovic.vic.gov.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Victorian-Protective-Data-Security-Framework-V2.1.pdf	Victorian Protective Data Security Framework	2023	Government of Victoria

https://www.utas.edu.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0007/1551769/Research-Data-Management-Procedure.pdf	Research Data Management Procedure	2024	University of Tasmania
https://digitalhealthcrc.com/wpcontent/uploads/2024/04/DHCRC-Call-to-Action-for-a-National-Data-Governance-Framework_Feb-2023_2024-UPDATE.pdf	Digital Transformation Of Healthcare In Australia Constrained	2023	Digital Health Cooperative Research Centre (DHCRC)
https://www.education.gov.au/aboutdepartment/resources/data-strategy-2023-2025	Department of Education Data Strategy	2023	Australian Government – Department of Education
https://www.vic.gov.au/information-management-whole-victorian-government	Information Management Framework (IMF) for the Victorian Public Service	2016	Victorian Government – Department of Premier and Cabinet
https://www.environment.vic.gov.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0027/667440/Data-Framework-Victoria-Unearthed-FINAL-v2.0.pdf	Victoria Uneearthed Data Framework	2023	Victoria state government
https://www.education.sa.gov.au/policies/shared/governance-framework.pdf	Governance Framework – Department for Education South Australia	2024	Funded and supported by the Commonwealth of Australia,
https://www.acs.org.au/insightsandpublications/reports-publications/sharing-data-in-trusted-frameworks.html	Sharing data in trusted frameworks	2021	Australian Computer Society
https://dex.dss.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/2024-03/1066-data-exchange-framework_0.pdf	Data Exchange Framework	2023	Australian government

https://www.library.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/2025-03/nla-ai-framework-1-0.pdf	Artificial Intelligence Framework	2024	National Library of Australia
https://about.unimelb.edu.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0031/99184/UoM_response_Data61_AI_Ethics_Framework.pdf	Artificial Intelligence: Australia's Ethics Framework University of Melbourne Response	2019	The University of Melbourne
https://www.education.gov.au/schooling/resources/australian-framework-generative-artificial-intelligence-ai-schools	Australian Framework for Generative Artificial Intelligence in Schools	2023	Australian government, department of education

Table 2- Global frameworks and guidelines

URL	Framework	Year	Origin
https://zenodo.org/records/11110082	UKDS Data Skills Framework	2024	UK
https://sfia-online.org/en/sfia-9	SFIA 9	2024	UK
https://edisonproject.eu/sites/edisonproject.eu/files/filefield_paths/edison_ds-bok-release2-v04.pdf	Data Science Body of Knowledge (DS-BoK)	2017	European Union
https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/ESRC-311023-SkillsNeededToSupportDataDrivenResearch-ESRCresponse.pdf	The Skills Needed in the Social Sciences to Support Data-Driven Research Across the Lifecourse	2023	UK
https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/ESRC-181222-DataDrivenResearchSkills-ScopingReport.pdf	ESRC Data-Driven Research Skills Scoping Report	2022	UK
https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8846/1/2022_Jisc_BDC_Individual_Framework.pdf	Jisc Building Digital Capabilities Framework	2024	US
https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/8862/1/2022_BDC_Researcher_Profile.pdf	Researcher role profile Six elements of digital capabilities	2022	UK
https://www2.itif.org/2021-us-digital-skills.pdf	Assessing the State of Digital Skills in the U.S. Economy	2021	US
https://dera.ioe.ac.uk/id/eprint/38346/1/Quantifying%20the%20UK%20Data%20Skills%20Gap%20-%20Full%20report%20-%20GOV.UK%20%28redacted%29.pdf	Quantifying the UK Data Skills Gap	2021	UK

https://unstats.un.org/bigdata/blog/2021/expo2020/sessions/24/presentations/Training%20TT_knowledge%20exchange_Expo%2027Jan-CF-FINAL.pdf	UN Big Data Competency Framework	2020	United Nations
https://ioaglobal.org/pdf/loA-Analyst-Competency-Framework.pdf	Institute of Analytics (IoA) Analyst Competency Framework	2023	UK
https://transform.england.nhs.uk/media/documents/NCF_Framework_Booklet.pdf	National Competency Framework for Data Professionals in Health and Care	2023	UK
https://www.cdbb.cam.ac.uk/files/010321cdbb_skills_capability_framework_vfinal.pdf	Skills and Competency Framework	2021	UK
https://dalicitizens.eu/index.php/dali-data-literacy-framework-2/	DALI Data Literacy Framework	2023	European Union
https://hochschulforumdigitalisierung.de/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/HFD_AP_Nr_53_Data_Literacy_Framework.pdf	Future Skills: A Framework for Data Literacy	2020	Germany
https://www.imda.gov.sg/-/media/imtalent-portal-revamp/3-guidances/skills-planning/sf-ict/ict-navigation-tool-2020.pdf	ICT Skills Framework Navigation Tool	2020	Singapore
https://hub.jncc.gov.uk/assets/6ef949ed-1c22-438f-b2f7-fd4818ec4566	JNCC Data Skills Framework	2018	UK
https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2019/05/oecd-skills-strategy-2019_g1g9ff20.html	OECD Skills Strategy	2019	OECD

https://www.oecd.org/content/dam/oecd/en/publications/reports/2021/04/the-oecd-framework-for-digital-talent-and-skills-in-the-public-sector_f6fb7838/4e7c3f58-en.pdf	The OECD Framework for Digital Talent and Skills in the Public Sector	2021	OECD
https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/7d01c8ae-dca0-55cf-ad21-b2df0a03d207/content	Digital Skills: Frameworks and Programs	2020	World Bank
https://nrc-publications.canada.ca/eng/view/author/version/?id=b2e645d4-eb38-4378-b6a8-763cc8d25d8a	Three Frameworks for Data Literacy	2023	Canada
https://resources.data.gov/keywords/data-skills/	Assessing Data Skills Playbook	2020	US
https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/SpecialPublications/1500-18/NIST.SP.1500-18r2.pdf	NIST Research Data Framework	2023	US
https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/UKRI-201020-UKInfrastructure-opportunities-to-grow-our-capacity-FINAL.pdf#page=6.07	The UK's research and innovation infrastructure: opportunities to grow our capability	2020	UK
https://theodi.cdn.ngo/media/documents/2020-05-Data-Skills-Framework-Print-at-home.pdf	Data Skills Framework	2020	UK
https://resources.data.gov/assets/documents/fds-data-ethics-framework.pdf	Federal Data Strategy Data Ethics Framework	2019	US

https://www.data.govt.nz/assets/Uploads/Training/Data-Capability-Framework/Data-Capability-Framework-Guide.pdf#page=2.19	Data capacity framework		Australia/New Zealand
https://www.skillnetireland.ie/uploads/attachments/Study-of-Data-and-Digital-Skills-for-all-non-IT-Roles-across-Multiple-Industries.pdf	Data Skills Training	2023	Ireland
https://data.jncc.gov.uk/data/6ef949ed-1c22-438f-b2f7-fd4818ec4566/JNCC-Report-590-FINAL-WEB.pdf	Data Skills Framework: A generic approach to assessing and developing data related competencies and skills	2018	UK
https://www.cspsefpc.gc.ca/tools/jobaids/pdfs/data-competency-framework-eng.pdf	Data Competency Framework	2020	Canada
https://analyticsinstitute.org/asset/025D5353-9F76-43A4-8700A786050B3446/#:~:text=A%20new%20Data%20and%20Analytics,in%20a%20data%2Ddriven%20world.&text=A%20graduated%20Data%20Skills%20Framework,in%20a%20data%2Ddriven%20world.	Data skill framework	2023	Ireland
https://digitaltwinhub.co.uk/download/skills-competency-framework/	Skills and Competency Framework	2020	UK
https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_CNES_Putting_Skills_First_2023.pdf	Putting Skills First: A Framework for Action	2023	World Economic Forum
https://www.digitalskillnet.ie/util/file.php?f=Li4vdXBsb2Fkcy9tZWRpYXBvb2wvZ2xvYmFsX2RhdGFfZnJhbWV3b3JrLnBkZg	Data Skills framework		Ireland

<https://sfia-online.org/en/sfia-9/sfia-9-release-notes/data-and-analytics-skills> Data and analytics skills

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/649038075f7bb7000c7facf7/DDaT_Playbook_Final.pdf The Digital, Data and Technology

2023

Table 3 Research Software Engineering frameworks and guidelines

URL	Framework	Year
https://centaur.reading.ac.uk/105313/1/SB_RSE_paper.pdf	The Research Software Encyclopedia	2022
https://www.pure.ed.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/65195747/DR2012_12_1_.pdf	Edinburgh Research Explorer, The Research Software Engineer	2012
https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-022-01516-2	Why science needs more research software engineers	2022
https://arxiv.org/pdf/2311.11457	Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of a Research Software Engineer	2024
https://fairsfair.eu/sites/default/files/3.%20FinnishRoadshow_DataSteward_coordination.pdf	Professionalising the Research Software Engineer and Data Steward roles - towards models for collaboration and good practice	2021
https://cacm.acm.org/opinion/investigating-research-software-engineering-toward-rse-research/	Investigating Research Software Engineering: Toward RSE Research	2025
https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/openaccessgovernment.org-The-development-of-research-software-engineering-as-a-profession.pdf	The development of research software engineering as a profession	2023

https://www.se-rwth.de/essay/Research-Software-Engineering/	Research Software Engineering	2024
https://lvmiranda921.github.io/notebook/2020/11/15/data-science-swe/	How to improve software engineering skills as a researcher	2021
https://zenodo.org/records/10073233	Research Software Engineers: Creating a Career Path—and a Career	2023
https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10664-008-9102-8	Guidelines for conducting and reporting case study research in software engineering	2008
https://arxiv.org/pdf/2202.07519	Social Science Theories in Software Engineering Research	2022
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/260985102_A_FRAMEWORK_FOR_SOFTWARE_MODELLING_IN_SOCIAL_SCIENCE_RESEARCH	A Framework for software modelling in social science research	2013
https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3510003.3510076	Social science theories in software engineering research	2005
https://eva.fing.edu.uy/pluginfile.php/88252/mod_label/intro/Rivera-Ibarra%2010.pdf	Competency Framework for Software Engineers	2010
https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0950584922001446	The essential competencies of software professionals: A unified competence framework	2022

https://cacm.acm.org/opinion/investigating-research-software-engineering-toward-rse-research/	Investigating Research Software Engineering: Toward RSE Research	2025
https://zenodo.org/records/4287860	An open source textbook for research software engineering	2020
https://zenodo.org/records/4289335	eResearch & Data Skills Summit	2020
https://oceanrep.geomar.de/id/eprint/61464/1/CACM2025.pdf	Investigating Research Software Engineering: Toward RSE Research	2025
https://lib.jucs.org/article/22574/	A Systematic Mapping Study on Soft Skills in Software Engineering	2019
https://digitalcommons.csbsju.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1035&context=csci_pubs	Research Software Science: Expanding the Impact of Research Software Engineering Software Engineering	2022
Towards a National Research Software Engineering Capability in Arts and Humanities Research: a Roadmap	Towards a National Research Software Engineering Capability in Arts and Humanities Research: a Roadmap	2025
https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.06484	10 quick tips for making your software outlive your job	2025
https://oceanrep.geomar.de/id/eprint/61464/1/CACM2025.pdf	Investigating Research Software Engineering: Toward RSE Research	2025
https://literatur.thuenen.de/digbib_extern/dn067237.pdf	Foundational Competencies and Responsibilities of a Research Software Engineer	2023
https://zenodo.org/records/6623556	FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles)	2022

https://zenodo.org/records/7660245	FAIR4RS - FAIR for Research Software	2023
https://zenodo.org/records/6340732	The Overlap Between FAIR for Research Software and Open Science	2022
https://zenodo.org/records/6374314	FAIR4RS Software (FAIR4RS)	2022
https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01710-x	Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software	2022
https://proceedings.scipy.org/articles/Majora-342d178e-015.pdf	Software Engineering as Research Method: Aligning Roles in Econ-ARK	2022

Table 4 Frameworks and guidelines for Indigenous data governance

URL	Framework	Year
https://yumi-sabe.aiatsis.gov.au/sites/default/files/outputs/2023-11/Indigenous%20Data%20Governance%20in%20Australia.pdf	Indigenous Data Governance in Australia: Towards A National Framework	2023
https://www.niaa.gov.au/resource-centre/framework-governance-indigenous-data	Framework for Governance of Indigenous Data	2024
https://www.lowitja.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/Taking-Control-of-Our-Data-Discussion-Paper.pdf	Taking Control of Our Data	2024
https://mbspgh.unimelb.edu.au/centres-institutes/onemda/research-group/indigenous-data-network/projects/improving-indigenous-research-capabilities-project	Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities: An Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research Data Commons	2023
https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5b3043afb40b9d20411f3512/t/63ed934fe861fa061ebb9202/1676514134724/Communique-Indigenous-Data-Sovereignty-Summit.pdf	Indigenous Data Sovereignty	2018
https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&opi=89978449&url=https://policy.unisq.edu.au/documents/21423PL/pdf&ved=2ahUKEwiHnc3EtZqOAxVsTmwGHYgsLbkQFnoECB4QAAQ&usq=AOvVaw3M7Vw8ZXqSQfOIkKYIPwjB	Research Data Management and Indigenous Data Governance Schedule	

https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/completed/indigenous-evaluation/strategy/indigenous-evaluation-guide.pdf	Indigenous Evaluation Strategy by the Productivity Commission	2020
https://www.lowitja.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/Indigenous-Data-Sovereignty-Policy-Brief.pdf	Indigenous Data Sovereignty Policy Brief	2023
https://iphcc.ca/wp-content/uploads/ninja-forms/2/Data-Governance-Framework-Appendix.pdf.pdf	Data Governance Framework Appendix	2023
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Social Science Research Infrastructure Network

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